

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fIOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 5.3

CITY ECOSYSTEM DESIGN

Due date of deliverable: 30/11/2021
Actual submission date: 28/03/2022
Start date of project: 01/06/2019 Duration (36 Months)
Dissemination Level: Public ✓

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.*

DELIVERABLE

Work Package	WP5 Pilots
Deliverable	City Ecosystem Design
Task(s)	Task 5.3 – City Ecosystem Analysis:Stakeholder, Logistics and Governance [M06-M30]
Document Name	City Ecosystem Design
Due Date	M30
Submission Date	M34
Dissemination Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> P – Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO – Confidential
Deliverable Lead	Stichting Waag Society (Waag)
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Reviewers	CBS, MAT
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This deliverable will illustrate the blueprint of economic loop models for each specific city resource stream: textiles, packaging, wood, plastics, water, agrifood, housing and electricity. The design is the result of the analysis and elaboration of information concerning logistics, system stakeholders, governance and business models.
Keywords	logistics; stakeholders; governance; material flows
Statement of Originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author (s)	Organization	Description
D5.3 v0.1	23-02-2022	Margherita Soldati, Letizia Chiappini	Waag	<i>First draft</i>
D5.3 v0.2	7-03-2022	Margherita Soldati, Letizia Chiappini, Pilot cities (validation round), Apurva Singh, Elodie Chatel, Antoine Coudard, Vicky Miles	Waag, Metabolic, pilots	<i>Change by partners</i>
D5.3 v0.3	18-03-2022	Margherita Soldati, Apurva Singh, Elodie Chatel, Antoine Coudard, Vicky Miles	Waag, Metabolic	<i>Change by partners</i>
D5.3 v1.0	28-03-2022	Margherita Soldati, Apurva Singh, Elodie Chatel, Antoine Coudard, Vicky Miles	Waag, Metabolic	<i>Final version by the consortium to be submitted to the EC.</i>

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

DELIVERABLE	1
REVISION HISTORY	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND KEYWORDS	7
LIST OF FIGURES	10
INTRODUCTION	11
1.1 About REFLOW	11
1.2 REFLOW Vision	11
1.3 Introduction to the Deliverable	11
1.4 Scope and Objectives	13
1.5 Connections to other REFLOW deliverables	14
1.6 Theoretical Background and Exercise Construction	16
1.6.1 Creation of a Blueprint	16
1.6.2 Existing Resources	16
1.7 Circular Loops Diagram	17
1.7.1 Introduction	17
1.7.2 Identification of linear steps on the value chain	20
1.7.3 Identification of all possible loops	20
1.8 Selection of Two Use Cases	21
1.9 Backcasting Exercise - Identifying the Levers	22
1.10 Identification of the goal and validation of REFLOW activities	22
1.11 Identification of Activities Barriers, Levers and Stakeholders	23
1.12 Critical Actions, Stakeholder Mapping and Dependencies	25
2. AMSTERDAM PILOT	27
2.1 Pilot Introduction	27
2.2 Ecosystem Mapping	27
2.3 Selected Use Cases	30
2.3.1 Swapshop	30
2.3.2 Isolation Gowns	36
3. BERLIN PILOT	42
3.1 Pilot Introduction	42
3.2 Ecosystem Mapping	43
3.3 Selected Use Cases	45
3.3.1 Wastewater Heat Radar	45

4. CLUJ PILOT	53
4.1 Pilot Introduction	53
4.2 Ecosystem mapping	54
3.3 Selected use cases	55
3.3.1 Retrofit Kit	55
5. MILAN PILOT	61
5.1 Pilot Introduction	61
5.2 Ecosystem mapping	62
5.3 Selected use cases	64
5.3.1 Foody Zero Waste	65
5.3.2. Food Market 4.0	71
6. PARIS PILOT	79
6.1 Pilot Introduction	79
6.2 Ecosystem mapping	79
6.3 Selected use cases	81
6.3.1 DIMENSIONNEUSE	81
6.3.2 RE-LABEL	90
7. VEJLE PILOT	96
7.1 Pilot Introduction	96
7.2 Ecosystem mapping	97
7.3 Selected Use Cases	99
7.3.1 REMA 1000	99
7.3.2. Plastics in healthcare products: Sofiegården	105
8. CONCLUSION	111

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND KEYWORDS

Abbreviations:

B2B: Business-to-Business
B2C: Business-to-Consumer
CE: Circular Economy
EMF: Ellen McArthur Foundation
EU: European Union
GHG: Greenhouse Gases
LCA: Life Cycle Analysis
IP: Intellectual Property
ODD: Open Data Dashboard
RCGT: Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit
REFLOW OS: REFLOW Operating System
RFID: Radio-Frequency Identification
SROI: Social Return on Investment
WPs: Work Packages

Key words:

Circular business models Circular business models are business models that are cycling, extending, intensifying, and/or dematerialising material and energy loops to reduce the resource inputs into and the waste and emission leakage out of an organisational system

Circular city A circular city is a city where the circular economy principles are implemented and result in a resilient system that facilitates new kinds of social, environmental, technological, and economic activities. Examples of which can be the strengthening of competitiveness and the generation of employment.

Circular Economy (CE) A Circular Economy is an alternative to a dominant linear industrial model of design, produce, purchase, consume and dispose. A circular model aims to redefine growth and a positive societal impact. For its development a systemic approach and a deep transformation of habits and behaviour are needed. It entails a transition from using finite energy resources, to using renewable ones (designing the concept of waste out of the system), while building economic, natural and social impact. Although starting from different materials in REFLOW, the focus of the circular economy gradually extends beyond these issues related to material management and covers other aspects such as the social impact, technological aspects and the evolution of urban governance

structures. Since the Circular Economy is purposive, but isn't just about sustainability environmentally and economically, the social components are fundamental for this transition to happen. This happens in mindset and cultural rituals: from the way we design, produce, consume, purchase and dispose, all the way to how we see and value existing, or even abundant, resources present in the local environments.

Economic loop	The flow of resources, information and money moving from one agent to another. In a circular economy, the goal is to slow, narrow and close resource loops
Iterative design	Iterative design is a design methodology based on continual improvement of a concept, prototype, design or product. In Reflow, iterative design will be conceived with an agile structure enabling continuous improvements and adjustments of the local pilot projects in a collaborative manner.
Levers	Actions and interventions promoting transformative change
Life cycle thinking	Approach of accounting for economic, environmental and social impacts across all stages of a product or services life cycle.
Recovery	Process of extracting material, energy or water from the waste stream for reuse or recycling.
Recycling	The collection, sorting and processing of disposed materials for use in another manufacturing process.
Refurbished materials	Discarded materials or products that are typically repaired, refinished and sanitized to serve their original function.
Regenerative city	A regenerative city moves beyond sustainability, and develops a restorative, mutually beneficial relationship with the natural and social systems that sustain it. In Reflow, the road to generative urban development will be achieved through the attention to the social, environmental, technological and economic dimensions.
Regenerative economy	An approach in which products and services replenish their own sources of energy, water and materials in a closed-loop system.
Remanufacturing	Process of recovery, disassembly, repair and sanitizing components or parts for resale and reuse.
Renewable resources	Materials, energy and water sources that replenish themselves after human extraction within a finite amount of time.
Resource efficiency	A percentage of the total resources consumed that make up the final product or service.

Reuse	Using a product or material again, either for the same or an alternative function.
Systems thinking	Systems thinking is the ability or skill to perform problem solving in complex systems. A system is an entity with interrelated and interdependent parts; it is defined by its boundaries and is more than the sum of its parts (subsystem). Changing one part of the system affects other parts and the whole system, with predictable patterns of behaviour. Furthermore, the individuals working as part of a system are components as well, therefore contributing to its outcome
Urban Metabolism	Urban metabolism is a model that examines material and energy flows within cities as complex systems, as various social, environmental, economic governance and technological factors shape them.
Value proposition	A value proposition is a promise of value to be delivered, communicated, and acknowledged.

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1:** Visual reading guide of this document
- Figure 2:** The REFLOW framework
- Figure 3:** Butterfly Model from Ellen Macarthur Foundation
- Figure 4:** Biological cycles description
- Figure 5:** Technical cycles description
- Figure 6:** Identification of linear steps on the value chain exercise
- Figure 7:** Circular Loops Diagram mapped out as a tool by WP7 for the Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit
- Figure 8:** Amsterdam T5.3 Step 1 example
- Figure 9:** Amsterdam T5.3 Step 2 example
- Figure 10:** Amsterdam T5.3 Step 3 example
- Figure 11:** Amsterdam T5.3 Step 4 example and list of Levers defined in D1.3
- Figure 12:** Amsterdam T5.3 Final blueprint: Critical actions, stakeholders, levers, partnerships
- Figure 13:** Amsterdam's Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3
- Figure 14:** Amsterdam's first Swapshop location on Haarlemmerdijk street
- Figure 15:** Critical actions co-identified for the Swapshops with Amsterdam pilot to achieve 5-year goal
- Figure 16:** The Circular Isolation Gown developed by the Amsterdam Pilot
- Figure 17:** Critical actions co-identified for the Circular Isolation Gowns solution with Amsterdam pilot to achieve 5-year goal
- Figure 18:** Berlin's Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3
- Figure 19:** Screenshot from the Berlin Wastewater Heat Radar interface showing an area with available data
- Figure 20:** Screenshot from the Berlin Wastewater Heat Radar interface showing the estimation of extraction power vs. heating load with radius function
- Figure 21:** Critical actions co-identified for the wastewater reuse solution with Berlin pilot to achieve 5-year goal
- Figure 22:** Cluj-Napoca's Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3
- Figure 23:** Light and movement sensors
- Figure 24:** Critical actions co-identified for the Retrofit Kit solution with Cluj pilot to achieve 5-year goal
- Figure 25:** Milan's Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3
- Figure 26:** BOTTO device
- Figure 27:** Telegram BOT interacting between wholesalers and organisations
- Figure 28:** Critical actions co-identified for Foody Zero Waste with the Milan pilot to achieve the 5-year goal
- Figure 29:** Smart scale system with RFID reader
- Figure 30:** Reusable and foldable crates with RFID tag
- Figure 31:** Critical actions co-identified for Food Market 4.0 with the Milan pilot to achieve the 5-year goal
- Figure 32:** Paris Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3.
- Figure 33:** Dimensionneuse system used during the use case
- Figure 34:** Dimensionneuse database
- Figure 35:** Critical actions co-identified for Dimensionneuse. with the Paris pilot to achieve the 5-year goal
- Figure 36:** RE-Label certificate
- Figure 37:** Critical actions co-identified for Re-Label with the Paris pilot to achieve the 5-year goal
- Figure 37:** Vejle's first version Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3
- Figure 38:** Vejle's Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3.
- Figure 39:** Critical actions co-identified for REMA's 1000 solution with the Vejle pilot to achieve the 5-year goal
- Figure 40:** Critical actions co-identified for Sofiegaarden solution with the Vejle pilot to achieve the 5-year goal

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 About REFLOW

REFLOW is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, REFLOW uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualise and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximise multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project provides best practices aligning market and government needs in order to create favourable conditions for the public and private sector to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. REFLOW is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle and assess their social, environmental and economic impact, by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

1.2 REFLOW Vision

A circular and regenerative city in REFLOW represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to social, environmental and economic impact; where technology is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and support resilience of social and ecological systems; where governance is collaborative and inclusive; where knowledge is shared, and stakeholders are active and involved.

1.3 Introduction to the Deliverable

The core focus of this task was for each of the pilot cities to redesign the local ecosystem for their specific topic. Through co-design, co-creation and reflective practice the cities deepened their understanding of current logistics, system stakeholders, governance and business models, and came to redesign these into future proof models that can promote the concept of regenerative cities. The challenge was to design systems that fit the needs of people on the one hand, and the needs of the planet on the other, aiming towards sustainable economic development. Through this task we came to understand what stakeholders, models and systems were characteristic for specific city streams, and what future actions each city pilot could take to further progress towards a circular system.

The process undertaken by T5.3 City Ecosystem Analysis: Stakeholder, Logistics and Governance to map the local ecosystem and creation of a blueprint for action for each selected pilot solution is documented within this report, as are the results derived. D5.3: City Ecosystem Design is organised into two main sections - first section laying out the methodology and setup of the process taken with each pilot, along with the description of how the process has developed over time through co-creation with the pilots. The second section covers the outcomes of this process with each REFLOW pilot city and the solutions (a.k.a. use cases) selected for this exercise.

Included within each pilot chapter are the following sections:

- **Pilot introduction:** A brief introduction to the scope and focus of the pilot in relation to their activities within REFLOW
- **Ecosystem mapping:** The overview of circular loops that reflect the current and future actions of the pilots in relation to the current linear system of their focus area. This is shown as a Circular Loops Diagram (see section 1.7) capturing materials, local actors, actions, and cycles of iterations within the pilots' activities.
- **Selected use cases:** This section goes in depth into selected solutions developed by the pilots and the blueprint for future actions co-developed with the pilots in the form of a 5 year timeline and a summary of critical action. The aspects covered in this section for each use case are:
 - What is the use case about?
 - What is the goal of this solution in 5 years?
 - What are the barriers towards reaching this goal?
 - What needs to be done to reach this goal?
 - What are the required critical actions and who should be involved?
- **Critical dependencies** (if any): This section highlights any critical dependencies or points of failure noted within the timeline that may require further attention.
- **Impacts:** This brief section provides an overview of where the impacts for social, economic, environmental and governance dimension of the solution can be found within REFLOW.

1.3.1 Reading Guide

This document is organised in four main sections. The **first section**, visualised in orange figure 1 below, outlines the general scope of the task this deliverable reports on and the connections with the other deliverables. The **second section** (blue) outlines the theoretical background of the task 5.3, the several steps the pilots undertook during the main exercises developed in this task: Circular Loop Diagram and Backcasting exercise. This section serves as a guide to read **section three** (green) where the pilot's use cases are outlined in detail and unfolded through the Backcasting exercise. The first and fourth sections both reflect on how this task highlights the connections between the different deliverables. Finally the **last section** (black) outlines the conclusion, touching upon what the pilot's next steps are, the lesson learnt and how this task can be replicated by other cities.

D5.3 City Ecosystem Design

Figure 1: Visual reading guide of this document

1.4 Scope and Objectives

The main objective of this task is to develop a system change blueprint for each of the six pilot cities involved (Amsterdam, Berlin, Milan, Paris, Vejle, and Cluj-Napoca) by assessing how the solutions developed by the pilots are situated within the current city ecosystem. The assumption is that through this mapping, pilots might be able to position their solutions within the circular transition of the system in a more nuanced manner, and effectively find opportunities to ameliorate the current linear system and future patterns of development. Simultaneously, the parallel goal of the task is to grasp the dynamics concerning how each pilot proceeds in proposing and developing its solutions. The proposed solutions are not only based on previous work and gathered knowledge, but they encompass the outcomes of all the actions that have been done until now by the pilots towards the circular transition of their city.

In the realisation of this task, the aim is to build up strategies that create a common language and way of reading each pilot's progress and activity. This strategy will strongly take into consideration how circular loops have been

achieved through activities within REFLOW, how it connects with key stakeholders and which governance levers needs to be activated in order for the specific solutions to be implemented. Further on the deliverable provides a set of key critical actions for each pilot solution to enable long term change.

Within the scope of this task, only a few solutions have been selected per pilot for an in-depth analysis. The full list of solutions developed by the pilots can be found in *D1.4 Validation and Performance Evaluation*. The reader should keep in mind certain aspects related to the set of solutions covered in this deliverable: different pilot cities have followed different strategies in development of their solutions. While some cities chose to diversify the solutions and develop prototypes on a smaller scale, others directed their work and resources to fewer, but more large-scale, comprehensive solutions. Therefore, the number of solutions is not in any way indicative of the pilot city efforts, as the solutions vary in scope, depth and level of progress.

1.5 Connections to other REFLOW deliverables

Task 5.3 plays a crucial role within the REFLOW Deliverables. The function of the task is the connection of different components of the project in relation to the solutions developed by the pilots through activities within REFLOW. First, it builds up and elaborates on existing knowledge along with previous tasks as background to develop further actions (see section 1.5.2). The ecosystem design exercise uses the levers, defined in the REFLOW framework and fully described in D1.3 REFLOW Framework (see section 3.4.4), to identify and assign the relevant lever required within each solution. Task 5.3 is positioned across the micro to meso level within the REFLOW framework (Figure 1 below), as it looks at individual solutions developed by the pilots (micro level) and places them in the city-wide ecosystem (meso level).

Figure 2: The REFLOW framework

Second, T5.3 has worked parallelly with:

- D5.4 (technological solutions) to further elaborate on the same set of solutions that the pilots have developed keeping implementation and viability in mind.
- D7.5, Chapter 3: *Business Models*, the business models developed for the solutions with potential for commercial exploitation are described. Not all pilot solutions were determined to have such potential, and consequently the six pilots have developed a different number of business models. These business models support the future commercialisation of project results, which can contribute to growing the body of businesses who operate according to circular principles.

The outcomes of the T5.3 exercises have further fed into upcoming deliverables, where:

- The scaling factors for the environmental impacts of each solution were identified to support the calculation of CO2 emission reductions and other impacts, which will be reported in D3.3
- By mapping the stakeholders relevant at each step of the solution timeline, T5.3 helped in the initial identification of relevant stakeholders for the Social Returns on Investment (D1.5).
- D4.4 in turn captures the learnings gained so far from the use of the toolkit, such as the proofs of concept that offer insights about the process of urban transition. The learnings from T5.3 have been thoroughly scrutinised and presented under the different 'infrastructuring' levels, to provide a series of governance models that indicate potential collaborative pathways towards circular and regenerative cities.

In short, the core of task 5.3 is to connect multiple dimensions, develop future actions, and assemble new resources for other tasks to be implemented on the ground in the future. As a combination, deliverable 5.3 shows which strategies and methodologies have been adopted and how those have been practically applied within each pilot city: towards the creation of a final blueprint that highlights the most critical actions needed for their goals to succeed, the stakeholders and partnerships involved and the levers that need to be pulled for each specific action.

1.6 Theoretical Background and Exercise Construction

1.6.1 Creation of a Blueprint

Taking into account the fact that pilots are extremely diverse, in terms of compositions of actors, governance structure, and existing policies, another important pillar to achieve was to develop a common methodology that could be useful to share pilot's paths and work production in a similar way both visually and practically. The following section is dedicated to showing how the theoretical background has been applied to this task and what do the pilots have in common. The common ground on which each pilot is starting their process is the deployment of material in the whole flow. Accordingly, it has been decided to introduce both the conceptual Circular Loops Diagram, and an adapted diagram used for each use case. The conceptual model acts as a starting point to map out in a visual and adherent way a value chain adapted to pilots, while the diagram allows us to identify and select specific value chains, set of actions, and relevant actors that weave together from circular loops and drive system change. Specifically, the Circular Loops Diagram shows us a pattern on how the logistics have been structured in each city, in other words, mapping out the flows of material and consequently designing new circular loops.

1.6.2 Existing Resources

This task builds its ground on a lot of existing knowledge coming from the work developed by pilots and WPs in the first years of REFLOW projects.

There have been many tools and strategies used to map out the actions undertaken by the pilot in order to reach their objectives. These tools and strategies have been important resources that constituted the building blocks for a first analysis of the pilot's state of the art and were crucial for starting the development of task 5.3.

Without going into details, these are the existing resources that functioned as building ground for this task:

- The latest **Pilot Action Plans** produced in the deliverable D1.3 create a complete storyline out of the resources and knowledge collected in the project from the start. This deliverable illustrates for each pilot city their contexts, the pathways to change, their main scenarios and their implementation ideation, their envisioned impact and challenges, their KPIs.
With the objective in mind to understand and assess the relevance of the discussed scenarios proposed by the pilots, scenarios have been deployed, building around them more information and knowledge. Moreover, these scenarios have been concurrently applied with the pilot's KPIs, in which the ideation phase has served to corroborate the previously generated knowledge and understand how to concretely implement them. Stakeholders and levers result crucial in the applicability of the scenarios and the entire ecosystem analysed in this task (5.3).
- **Theory of Change (ToC)**, which accompanies the REFLOW project from the start, is used in REFLOW as a baseline for common understanding in the project. The methodology links activities, outputs, and outcomes by describing the pathway to change, through which the REFLOW pilot cities and the project itself expect to generate the desired impact.
This information supported the co-validation of the main scenarios and pathways each pilot would undertake to develop their solutions.
- **Material Flow Analysis**, produced by Metabolic in D3.2, is a systematic assessment of the flows and stocks of materials defined in space and time. It is a method that quantifies flows and stocks of resources within a defined system's boundary. Within task 5.3, each pilot used their MFA to capture and examine, through the analysis of the material flows, what are the main areas in need of interventions.
- **Pilot's REFLOW OS solutions**, which were outlined in parallel with the execution of task 5.3. Noticeably, the two tasks influenced and built on each other. In the effort of the pilots to develop and outline the solutions that needed to be implemented with task 5.4, the execution of task 5.3 created the environment to deepen and better understand why these solutions would have been the most impactful in the project.

1.7 Circular Loops Diagram

1.7.1 Introduction

The Circular Loops Diagram is a Circular Economy concept represented by a "butterfly" diagram. According to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, "This chart shows us a continuous flow of technical and biological materials through their "value circle". This diagram helps you mapping the specific value chains and actions to form circular loops and drive systems change. The tool has been adapted by Metabolic from the [Circular Economy Butterfly diagram](#) developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation to include a composite of both material-based actions and service-based actions. The diagram was also expanded to distinguish between current actions and future potential connections within the loops.

As also described in the Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit ([RCGT](#)) in WP4, the [Circular Loops Diagram tool](#) helps cities move from vision to opportunities for a transition to a circular economy framework. To kickstart such

a complex transition, the very first step is envisioning and mapping possible loops to move away from linear value chains. Circular loops identified can be further turned into business model ideas: the challenge is to design systems that fit the needs of people on the one hand, and the needs of the planet on the other, aiming for sustainable economic development.

Figure 3: Butterfly Model from Ellen MacArthur Foundation

On the original model, there are two sides to be observed with each a list of opportunities listed (Figure 3 and 4). The left side represents the biological cycles where the sustainable management and renewal of these biological resources and flows is imperative, while the right side presents the technical cycle, the sequence in charge of creating circular strategies for reducing, reusing, and recycling. The diagram pretends to show how to reduce the consumption of raw materials, how to reduce waste and gas emissions, and how to maintain a continuous loop where resources circulate and nature can be regenerated.

Figure 4: Biological cycles description & Figure 5: Technical cycles description

The Circular Loops Diagram used in the REFLOW context incorporates in a single figure all the elements the pilots are tackling and are planning to tackle. This Circular Loops Diagram locates the principal materials on the relevant loop with the opportunities associated, with the specifications of the stakeholders involved, and the state of the loop (current or future). The Model was modified to represent in a comprehensive manner the ecosystem of loops and materials to focus on.

During a series of one-on-one workshops with each pilot, the main activities have been to redesign and break down in simple steps the Circular Loops Diagram to be consistent with the REFLOW approach. The aim was to reach a Circular Loops Diagram chart draft per pilot incorporating all the possible loops mapped by each pilot and a selection of ideas that are translatable into business cases and are aligned with the solutions mapped out in the Theory of Change and Pilot Action Plans. For some pilots (Amsterdam, Vejle, Milan) the full ecosystem of activities around the chosen focal point was mapped, whereas for other pilots (Paris) only the specific use cases were directly mapped. In the case of the last two pilots (Cluj, Berlin), the Circular Loops Diagrams have been expanded

to mostly include possible future actions that build on current activities (Cluj, Berlin) . As the finalisation step of the Circular Loops exercise, the relevant loops for the selected use cases (one or two depending on the pilot) were developed further to showcase which circularity loops come into practice, these can be seen in the finalised Circular Loops Diagrams under each pilot.

1.7.2 Identification of linear steps on the value chain

In a first guided one-on-one workshop, pilots were asked to draft a list of the most relevant steps in their value chain representing the linear processes they were dealing with at that moment in the project.

Figure 6: Identification of linear steps on the value chain exercise

It has to be noted that even if the realisation of the exercise was meant to be straightforward, a few pilots have encountered several difficulties. The reason for these difficulties was the multiplicity of parallel value chains, as well as the overlapping of actors in the value proposition. Hence, the exercise has unravelled important aspects that need to be taken into consideration to organise actors into linear, connected, and coherent chains.

1.7.3 Identification of all possible loops

In a second one-on-one workshop session, the pilots have been guided through a second exercise to finalise the Circular Loops Diagram: connect the actors on their linear chains by creating all possible (existing and non-existing) loops. This exercise would show how materials would circulate back to ensure a continuous flow of resources. During this workshop, pilots pointed out loops that were coherent with the work they were currently developing but could also use this exercise as a moment to expand their vision and possibilities.

While creating these connection loops, pilots also started to identify actors (stakeholders) as additional steps on their loops that were/ would be crucial for the loop to “function”, as well as understanding the type of impact their solution meant in a circular model (recycle/ regenerate/ maintain/ etc.)

Figure 7: Circular Loops Diagram mapped out as a tool by WP7 for the Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit

The Circular Loops Diagram process as described has also been mapped out by the WP4 in the Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit ([RCGT](#)) in a step-by-step guide. This resource is conceived to support the design and development of collaborative governance arrangements for the transition to circular and regenerative cities. The objective is to showcase the tools used by pilot cities within REFLOW, but also potential tools that other cities can use in order to support circular action plans and specific collaborative governance activities.

1.8 Selection of Two Use Cases

At the end of this exercise, after all the loops have been identified, pilots were asked to select two of them. These two chosen loops selected as use cases are then further elaborated upon through in-depth exercises to help

better identify and dissect goals, activities, barriers, stakeholders, and levers needed to support and execute these use cases. In the majority of the cases, the two use cases identified in the Circular Loops Diagram, have been the same use cases elaborated in task 5.4, with the deployment of the Reflow OS technology.

1.9 Backcasting Exercise - Identifying the Levers

Backcasting can be defined as “generating a desirable future, and then looking backwards from that future to the present in order to strategize and to plan how it could be achieved¹ - Originating from the academic field of sustainable transition and innovation, this visioning method has increasingly been developed and used in non-academic circles to support public and private organisations to shape a future vision, and from there, devise a stepwise strategic plan on how to achieve this vision.

Within REFLOW, the Backcasting methodology was used and modified to fit the specificities of the pilots, and ultimately led to the creation of the Backcasting exercise in the form of a visual diagram that helps redesign the local ecosystem starting from previously identified use cases. Through co-design, this tool helps cities to deepen their understanding of current **logistics** and **stakeholders systems**, and come to redesign these into **future proof models** that promote the concept of regenerative cities.

After the Circular Loops Diagram has been completed and the two main use cases selected, the pilots proceed to execute (in a series of one-on-one workshops) the *Backcasting exercise*. This exercise constitutes the core of this task as it is critical to understand the extent of each activity conducted by the pilots.

To kick off this exercise, the pilot teams and Metabolic first defined a ‘*desirable future*’ in the form of a 5-year medium term goal for each use case. Following the definition of the goal, Metabolic invited each pilot to co-define the different challenges and barriers that could prevent the goal from being achieved. Then, based on these identified challenges, the pilot team was able to unfold for each use case a sequence of required actions to overcome these barriers, reach their objectives, and achieve the 5-year goal. For the majority of the pilots (except for Berlin and Cluj-Napoca), the Backcasting exercise has been executed twice, one time per use case. For each of the actions, the main ‘levers’, which can be defined as practices that create the required leverage to change cities’s metabolism towards circularity were identified from the list of 17 CE levers developed in REFLOW Deliverable D1.3. Then, the stakeholders required for these levers to operate were identified and their roles mapped across each timeline of the pilots. The definition of these stakeholders is therefore key for: 1) help each action to concretely take shape; and 2) shed light on potential partnerships that are essential to reach the ultimate goal. The steps mentioned above are further described below.

1.10 Identification of the goal and validation of REFLOW activities

In the first step of this exercise, the pilots define a concrete and attainable goal for each of the use cases identified in the previous session. Despite the three-year timeframe of the REFLOW project and that, at the time of the exercise, only one year of the project remained, the pilots were asked to define their achievable goals on a timeline of five years - so as to adopt a medium term perspective of their use case and ambitions. As a result, each

¹ J. Quist, P. Vergragt - Past and future of Backcasting: the shift to stakeholder participation and a proposal for a methodological framework Futures, 38 (2006), pp. 1027-1045

goal identified by the pilot will require actions beyond the REFLOW project that will build up on the activities conducted during REFLOW, hence the importance of framing the REFLOW use cases towards longer-term goals.

Figure 8: Amsterdam T5.3 Step 1 example

In the second step of the exercise, the pilots were asked to validate the main actions (previously sketched down by referring to their Action Plans) they were currently doing or planning to do in the remaining months of the REFLOW project. This step helps understand what level of development each use case will reach by the end of the project, and what will remain to be done in the following years to achieve the 5-year goal.

Figure 9: Amsterdam T5.3 Step 2 example

1.11 Identification of Activities Barriers, Levers and Stakeholders

In this **third step**, the pilots were asked to identify the potential barriers and challenges that could hinder or prevent the achievement of their co-defined five-year goal. A **brainstorm** session was therefore conducted with the pilot teams to gather all perspectives on the challenges their use-cases would face in the coming years.

Step 3 Identifying the gaps between REFLOW activities and the goal (5-10min)

In this step, we will **brainstorm gaps** in actions, resources, stakeholders that emerge from comparing your planned activities against the 5-year goal.

Limit this brainstorming session to 5 minutes. We will dive into depth during the next step!

Figure 10: Amsterdam T5.3 Step 3 example

The **fourth step** of this exercise sees the pilot focusing on three key aspects to achieve their defined goals.

What: Looking at the actions positioned in the timeline, the pilots were asked to co-define, in a stepwise manner the different actions that would need to happen to fill in the **gaps**, surpass the barriers, and make their vision a reality.

How: For each action just defined, the pilots were requested to define which Circular Economy **Levers** were relevant and must be pulled in order for each action to occur on the timeline. Within the Reflow Framework, outlined in the deliverable D1.3, 'Circular Economy Levers' are defined as practices that create the leverage to change towards circularity in cities (D1.3/3.4.4). In D1.3, the seventeen listed CE levers should, when activated, drive change towards economic circularity. The pilot cities can leverage these elements to develop their use cases and achieve their 5-year goal. In practice, the description of the levers must be extrapolated in order to make these actions possible and realistic in the coming years. The procedure was then to place relevant levers under each of the actions included in the timeline, and add any more specific contextual details to each lever.

Who: In this last phase of the Backcasting exercise, pilots were asked to identify the **stakeholders** required for each lever previously defined in order to enable each action to succeed - generally multiple actors were listed as necessary for any given action. This step helps identify potential stakeholder gaps in the pilots' own ecosystems.

Figure 11: Amsterdam T5.3 step 4 example and list of Levers defined in D1.3

1.12 Critical Actions, Stakeholder Mapping and Dependencies

Out of all the actions present on the timeline from the Backcasting exercise, critical actions were co-identified by each of the pilots to focus their attention on. Critical actions were defined as actions upon which the success of the use-case and the trajectory of the 5-year goal was most reliant on. For each critical action, the pilot conducted a more in-depth stakeholder mapping and identified stakeholders (type, organisation, or person) required to pull the levers listed in the critical action. Additionally, the pilots were asked to map out the level of partnership (formal, informal, or future) required or existing between stakeholders. For each critical action, the pilot team further elaborated sub-key-actions and levers to highlight which instruments were required to make this critical action a success. Lastly, the pilots were asked to reflect upon the critical dependencies between stakeholders and the timeline in which these actions unfold.

Figure 12: Amsterdam T5.3 Final blueprint: Critical actions, stakeholders, levers, partnerships

2. AMSTERDAM PILOT

2.1 Pilot Introduction

The REFLOW Amsterdam Pilot focuses on the way home textiles are discarded and reused, and how they can be returned to the local textile system. The current challenge is that home textiles are often wrongly discarded for two reasons: a lack of awareness, and due to sub-optimal ways of collecting textiles. More than 70% of home textiles will eventually be incinerated rather than reused in Amsterdam. Simultaneously, the demand for recycled material is growing slowly, due to an absence of commercial uptake.

The Amsterdam Pilot is composed of the **Municipality of Amsterdam**², **Pakhuis de Zwijger**³, **Waag**⁴ and **BMA Techne**⁵.

The Amsterdam Pilot has outlined two interconnected scenarios that tackle these challenges: a short-term scenario focusing on necessary behavioural change among its citizens, and a long-term scenario focusing on industrial impact, aiming to increase the provision of feedstock for the recycling industry, and, in turn, to increase the supply of products made of recycled resources. To hasten the transition from linear to circular textile flow, the Amsterdam Pilot has designed a strategy guiding a pathway to change. The strategy identifies distinct focal points connected with the short- and long-term scenarios, while developing an overarching roadmap for the last year of REFLOW and beyond.

- **Citizen scenario, short-term:** Increase of home textiles collection at city-level by engaging citizens through an awareness campaign. The campaign is centred on changing the way citizens process their home textiles with the outcomes of the discarding of fewer textiles, and the extension of the textile lifecycle.
- **Industrial scenario, long-term:** Exchange Network to connect manufacturers to the collected consumer textiles in order to decrease the percentage of virgin textile fibres used. Several strategies assist new ways of collecting textiles in order to generate more feedstock for recycling industries and therefore support the production of new products with recycled resources.

2.2 Ecosystem Mapping

Throughout the duration of the REFLOW project, numerous activities have been carried out by the pilot in order to engage and support the transformation in the Amsterdam Pilot region which have been reflected and analysed in T5.3 using the Circular Loops Diagram. The primary Circular Loops Diagram (v1) (see appendix) was focused on mapping the entire ecosystem of activities around textiles. The first version of the mapping identified the current linear textile flows, including the general steps and players in the textile producing process.

² <https://www.amsterdam.nl/en/>

³ <https://www.dezwijger.nl>

⁴ <https://waag.org>

⁵ <https://amsterdameconomicboard.com/samenwerkingspartner/bma-techne/>

In the second version of the Circular Loops Diagram, the solutions developed by the Pilot have been highlighted through the identification of loops and impacts for two main use cases:

1. Consumer textiles (Swapshop)
2. Healthcare textiles (Isolation gowns)

Figure 13: Amsterdam's Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3

The Circular Loops Diagram depicts what circularity loops the pilots are working on in relation to specific use cases developed through REFLOW activities, highlighting several closed loops for recycling, reusing and regeneration for present and future purposes. Each loop identifies the relevant stakeholders and current or future connections which are required to enable the function corresponding to the loop.

Regarding the **Consumer Textiles**, the following loops have been identified:

Recycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between <i>discarded material</i> and <i>raw material</i>, the unusable textile is sent to Boer Groep ⁶, an international textile recycling organisation for collection and sorting, and recycled in order to flow back at the top of the value chain. - Between <i>collection</i> and <i>raw material</i>, the unswappable cotton textile collected in the Swapshops is collected via the Denim Deal⁷, an agreement focused on making post-consumer recycling of textiles, mechanically recycled by Gamma⁸ (in Turkey) in order to flow back at the top of the value chain.
Reuse/Redistribute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between <i>collector</i> and <i>consumer/user</i>, part of the textile collected in the Swapshops is redistributed among citizens and local charities.
Remanufacture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between <i>raw material</i> and <i>parts manufacturer</i>, the recycled fibres are sent to spinners and knitters in EU to be remanufactured - Between <i>raw material</i> and <i>product manufacturer</i>, the recycled materials and fibres are sent to designers to manufacture new products.

Regarding the **Healthcare Textiles**, the following loops have been identified:

Refurbish/Remanufacture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between the <i>waste</i> and the <i>product manufacturer</i> - Via mechanical recycling between <i>waste</i> and <i>part/product manufacturer</i>
Reuse /Redistribute	Between the <i>collector</i> and the <i>consumer</i>

Additionally one more relevant loop connection has been identified:

Textile Material Design	Between the <i>part manufacturer</i> and the <i>raw material</i>
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The Circular Loops Diagram highlighted several closed loops for recycling, mechanical recycling, chemical recycling, refurbishing, manufacturing and maintaining the material resource, as well as for regenerating them. Two main use cases and their specific loops have been further explored within the Circular Loops Diagram: the disposable isolation gown within the healthcare sector, and Swapshops within the consumer textile sector.

⁶<https://www.boergroup.eu>

⁷<https://www.iamsterdam.com/en/business/news-and-insights/news/2020/amsterdam-signs-landmark-sustainable-denim-deal>

⁸ <https://www.gamarecycle.com>

2.3 Selected Use Cases

2.3.1 Swapshop

Introduction of the use case

The starting point of the discussion was that almost 9,000 tons per year of household textiles were sent to incineration, in 2019, with almost a third of these incinerated textiles that could be worn directly again and absorbed into the second-hand market, the focus of this use case. On the other hand, textiles that have been discarded properly into the textile waste stream, in 2019, (~3000 tons) are mostly shipped outside of the Netherlands, and therefore do not remain within Amsterdam's textile system. As a result, the necessity of removing textile from the residual waste streams by providing other used textile discarding options but also keeping the recovered textile within the local textile system became clear to the pilot team. The Swapshop concept was developed as an idea to resolve these challenges.

The Amsterdam Swapshop is a physical location in the centre of Amsterdam. Citizens can bring their (re-wearable) clothing to the location, and receive a voucher (Swaps) that is exchangeable to access clothing items brought in by others. The clothes received by the Swapshop are sorted, cleaned and, if necessary, repaired. The cost of this activity is covered by a service fee charged to Swapshop users. The Swapshop has the additional social benefit in the provision of employment opportunities for workers who may be disadvantaged in the employment market. The store also uses REFLOW OS tracking and tracing system to track and record the life of the item, as well as the user's journey. This monitoring allows the creation of a personal story for the item and thus creates a stronger emotional attachment with the item, encouraging users to create a personal connection with the garment that changes the perception of the textile's value. Meanwhile, the information gathered provides insights into behavioural motivations related to swapping, using and taking care of second-hand and otherwise used garments. Clothing that cannot be exchanged, i.e., those that are too worn to be reused, are manually sorted by staff and disposed of appropriately. For example, items made from textiles with a high percentage of cotton are directed to the Denim Deal (see Section 2.2.3.2). Other items might go, for example, to organisations such as Dress for Success⁹, or external enterprises like I-DID¹⁰, which produces new items out of the collected textiles for sale on the B2B market.

On April 24th, 2021, the City of Amsterdam became home to its first Swapshop, a noteworthy addition to the city's circular textile landscape (Figure 12). The Swapshop provides an important space for citizens to give new life to their wardrobe, where citizens can swap their old clothing for other pieces collected by the shop. The space also allows designers and other creatives to buy a small amount of discarded clothes for design projects or other creative purposes. The Swapshop aims to save 15 tons of discarded textiles each year by giving them a second life.

⁹ <https://dressforsuccess.org>

¹⁰ <https://www.i-did.nl>

Figure 14: Amsterdam's first Swapshop location on Haarlemmerdijk street

Description of the 5 years goal

The five year goal for Amsterdam Swapshop is to increase the flow of rewearable textiles and garments through second-hand shops in order to keep a high proportion of clothing in circulation within Amsterdam, diverting discarded textiles from incineration into secondary materials. The goals are to divert from incineration around 200 tons of clothes through Swapshops, by increasing the capacity of each Swapshop to at least 10 tons/year and opening more Swapshops across Amsterdam (about 20).

What are the barriers to this goal?

In the problem analysis definition, the Amsterdam Pilot has been able to further elaborate which are the different barriers in achieving the five year goal. Some **logistical barriers** are related to the physical spaces required to receive, sort, repair and re-distribute the textile items - for example, the first Swapshop open is limited to a maximum capacity of 4 tons per Swapshop; Additionally, it is key increase the amount of textile collected from Amsterdam residents - beyond the traditional ways of collection (drop-off, bins), but in practice, it is difficult to establish other collection process - for example the private collection of textiles (i.e. direct collection from house-to-house) is not currently permitted in the city. At a practical level, there is also a **gap in skills** in order to have enough staff capable of assessing the quality of textiles during the sorting process in Swapshops.

Additionally, a key **financial barrier** identified early on is connected to the overhead costs for establishment and running of Swapshops, and the costs of on-demand delivery and pick-up. In this context, it became key to highlight the **competition barriers** that Swapshop may face as independent commercial clothing retailers also seek to develop a second-hand market - for example connected to I:Collect¹¹ (H&M, C&A). This competition backed by large private investment could challenge Swapshops expansion in Amsterdam. Last but not least, the main **societal**

¹¹ <https://www.ico-spirit.com/en/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

barrier, as mentioned previously, the tendency of citizens to discard their textile items in the residual bins is still strong while their awareness of new end-of-life options for textiles is still limited.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

As previously mentioned, the identified barriers and challenges raised by the local actors have ignited the elaboration of a detailed timeline to scale the pilot’s solution after REFLOW and reach the defined goal. This table compiles, to begin, the key steps achieved within the REFLOW project by the Amsterdam Pilot, followed by all the necessary actions within the use case ‘Swapshop’ to reach the desired goal in a five year period, the latter having been developed within the Backcasting exercise.

During the Reflow project:

Action	REFLOW Framework Levers	Associated WPs
1. Research Material Experimentation	Prototyping and experimentation	WP3
2. Facilitate the promotion of circular textiles in educational programs and research	Capacity Building	WP6
3. Organise workshops with citizens and students on effective textile collection	Capacity Building	WP6
4. Create events with policy makers, experts, etc., publish articles, and work on Roadmap for circular textiles	Communication	WP7
5. Conduct experiments on manipulating and upcycling materials	Prototyping and Experimentation, Data & Tech	WP3 and WP5
6. Intensify collaborative actions with local networks and initiatives	Engaging and Convening	WP4
7. Create a business model for the Swapshop	Roadmap and strategies	WP7

Post-Reflow project

From year 1 to year 2:

- 8. Raise awareness on how to properly take care of clothes (repair/washing, etc.)
- 9. Perform a city-wide study to assess behaviours regarding second-hand clothes

10. Identify from the study the best-suited locations for the implementation of pick-up points and Swapshops

11. In communities where it is culturally not accepted to share clothes outside the community, install more textile bins and raise awareness

From year 2 to year 3:

12. Further develop the business model for the Swapshops in Amsterdam already developed during the REFLOW project in T7.5

13. Run campaigns to raise awareness about the possibility of swapping clothes

14. Open more Swapshops in Amsterdam and design logistical capacity training on behavioural studies previously conducted

15. Increase targeted diversion exchanges between the Swapshops for more clothes to be accessible for the population at each location

From year 3 to year 5:

16. Create a network between Swapshops and local retail actors.

17. Certain clothing stores now require clearer clothing labels to facilitate maintenance and keep clothes in use for longer.

18. Approach different scale designers to collaborate to implement design for longevity and to increase the value of the materials from the design phase.

Critical Actions

Some actions have been identified as critical (highlighted above) and have been detailed with levers and the stakeholder ecosystem required for the action.

Figure 15: Critical actions co-identified for the Swapshops with Amsterdam pilot to achieve 5-year goal

Along the Backcasting timeline, 17 actions were identified as necessary to the achievement of the 5-year goal for Swapshops. In order to substantiate the transformative potential of the goal, out of the total list of actions, four critical actions have been further expanded with the pilots and the key sub-actions and relevant stakeholders were highlighted.

Behavioural study

The behavioural study is the first critical action highlighted. It pertains to the city-wide study to assess behavioural patterns within communities. The key sub-actions consist of the research on cultural and consumption behaviour regarding reusing clothes, supported by the conduction of surveys to observe donation and recycling habits (*baseline assessment and engaging and convening levers*). Those sub-actions will allow the identification of the target group and clientele for the Swapshop (i.e., groups coming and not coming to the Swapshop). The principal stakeholder required is the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences¹² which will be involved in the research on collaborative practices and behavioural attitudes across urban communities.

Strengthen the Business model

This action is devoted to the further development of the business model for the Swapshops in Amsterdam. With the goal of expanding their reach past the REFLOW project, the proposed key sub-actions to further develop a strong business model consist of the creation of new connections between Swapshop and consumers, the implementation of a referral program that is connected to the to Stadspas¹³, and the implementation of a pilot in Rotterdam (*innovative partnerships and engaging and convening levers*).

Scale up

This action is oriented towards scaling up the Swapshop concept. The scaling up can be divided into two actions: the first one consists of creating more physical locations to exchange clothes, hence opening more Swapshops, and the second consists of optimising the efficiency and logistical capacity of each location. To make it possible, the network between Swapshops and local retailers must be reinforced, with new and future connections between municipalities and other actors to be created (*innovative partnerships and awareness raising levers*). To increase the logistical capacity of the Swapshops to handle more clothes, the employees will be required to sort more effectively, which will involve the Municipality of Amsterdam (*capacity building lever*). In parallel to getting the word out around the initiatives and the improvement of the internal logistics, one of the key steps to scale up is franchising the concept.

Create Network

This action is devoted to building strong and efficient partnerships between Swapshops and retailers to divert clothes from incineration (*innovative partnerships lever*). The main enabling stakeholder promoting this critical action is *Culture.Fashion*¹⁴, a open and value driven network for fashion, clothing and textile in The Netherlands that aims to bring individuals and organisations together and collectively work on a future-proof fashion sector in the country.

Promote clearer labels for clothing

The last action relates to the need of clearer clothing labels for clothing stores to facilitate maintenance and keep clothes in use for longer. This action will be crucial for the shift in textile use behaviours. However, it falls slightly more outside of the direct competencies and influence of the Swapshop organisation as compared to the other actions. To have clothing retailers and manufacturers improve their labels, a wide range of actors will

¹² <https://www.amsterdamuas.com>

¹³ <https://www.amsterdam.nl/stadspas/>

¹⁴ <https://www.culture.fashion/en>

have to be involved (*innovative partnerships* lever). Innovative and factually correct clothing labels will have to be developed by research institutions, such as Waag Institute, in collaboration with the Municipality of Amsterdam or other policy-makers, and key local retailers and awareness will have to be raised around the textile origins and life-cycle (*data and tech, and engaging and convening* levers).

Critical dependencies

Within this use case, the utmost critical dependency is related to the current model, which is highly dependent on individual consumer behaviours. A possible next step which could tackle the dependency would be the creation of partnerships with organisations (e.g. theatres, businesses) to apply and diffuse the swap clothing initiative in other contexts of regular clothing exchange. The adaptation of the model depends on local context (e.g. in business centres, swap high-end business clothes), as well as on initiatives to raise consumer awareness and understand better consumer behaviour patterns.

Impacts

The impacts related to the amount of textiles recovered through Swapshops are covered in detail in the deliverables D7.5, D1.5, and D3.3. In those, the business models, the social return on investments, and the environmental impacts are respectively described. In order to calculate the environmental impacts of this specific use case, a quantitative scaling factor was determined during within the scope of this deliverable and it is aligned with the pilot's goal to open 20 Swapshops in the next 5 years.

2.3.2 Isolation Gowns

Introduction of the use case

The Circular Isolation Gowns solution incorporates circular product design and the development of reusable isolation gowns in the healthcare sector using a track and trace technology. The solution is in collaboration with Clean Lease, the leasing company which provides textile products for the healthcare and hospitality industry. The solution aims to introduce reusable isolation gowns to a market which, as of today, uses solely disposable gowns. The Circular Isolation Gowns are designed to compete with the disposable ones on both functionality and comfort and can be washed up to 200 times. In addition, the attachment of a material passport (TAG) gives CleanLease¹⁵ insights into the material flow of the Circular Isolation Gowns. Value is created in this solution through the information defined by this process of track and trace through REFLOW OS and the transparency which this provides to the user. Currently, the prototype of the Circular Isolation Gowns has been finalised and the gowns will then undergo in-use trials to gather feedback on the ease of use, comfort, care, maintenance, the implication for use, and laundry logistics. The gowns are being locally produced by Makers Unite¹⁶ who will manufacture the first 3,000 gowns replacing a total of 300,000 disposable gowns.

¹⁵ <https://nl.cleanlease.com/nl/home>

¹⁶ <https://makersunite.eu>

Amsterdam Pilot has started to work on this specific use case as the use of disposable gowns within healthcare is notorious due to high hygiene regulations and cost-cutting measures. Throughout the Backcasting exercise, the pilot has pinpointed another crucial aspect in the transition, related to the cost of these disposable gowns. Hence, affordability in terms of price is one of the main drivers. The transition should avoid extra costs for the public healthcare system, which leads to a potential obstacle for managers in charge of purchasing these products. The new gowns must be able to compete in terms of price and comfort for the identified stakeholders. Thus, the transition is also dependent on external factors such as legislation that might favour or prevent certain trajectories in the transition from disposable gowns to recycled and sustainable ones. There is a need to make visible, and to prioritise in the imaginary and in practice a new sense of priority around the disposable gown. This imaginary should be built upon the priority of the shift towards re-use and away from single-use disposable gowns. Thus, beyond the REFLOW project, the idea is that reusable gowns must be shown to be beneficial and convenient on a sustainable level, and therefore worthy of a business case to transition from a linear to a circular production chain. The project will continue and move to the next stage: project LOCAAS - Local As A Service for which funding has been agreed and the planning for the coming 2 years is being made. In this second stage, around 25,000 isolation gowns will be produced and leased to Coordaan¹⁷, Olgv¹⁸ and other local hospitals.

Figure 16: The Circular Isolation Gown developed by the Amsterdam Pilot

Description of the 5 years goal

The 5-year goal of the reusable isolation gowns is a total of 5,000,000 disposable gowns being replaced with 50,000 reusable ones. Adjacent to this goal, is the behavioural goal of overcoming the reticence of people who

¹⁷ <https://www.cordaan.nl>

¹⁸ <https://www.olvg.nl>

work in public healthcare to change the current use of disposable gowns. It was therefore set as a goal that the recycled gowns must be as comfortable as the single-use ones and the price should remain unchanged or competitive.

What are the barriers to this goal?

There are different barriers to be taken into account within the Backcasting exercise. These barriers can be co-related to **logistical, financial, behavioural** aspects

Within the current linear supply chain, the companies that have developed the disposable gowns represent a sort of monopoly in production and distribution. The firms which provide the disposable gowns are concerned to remain in the market. The reason for the obstruction is the existing contracts stipulated between healthcare entities and disposable gown firms. The tension exists in terms of governance arrangements between stakeholders. In the supply chain, there are previous agreements with long-lasting contracts for purchasing disposable gowns for years. Hence, in this use case, there are four crucial dimensions: **time** (i.e., duration on the contract); **infrastructure** (i.e., logistic); **cost** (the same price of former disposable gowns), and **institutional dimensions**.

One of the main issues that pertains to the recycling system applied in essential sectors is the size and **scaling** of the material. In the specific case of the Amsterdam pilot, the size of the disposable gown and the potential scaling should be adequate to feed enough recycling capacity to supply recycled gowns in adequate volumes. The adequate number means that millions of gowns correspond to millions of uses, which consequently require secondary use for the material. The IP of one company may be a barrier to reaching the needed scale in order to achieve the final goal proposed in the loop.

Local manufacturing, capacity and infrastructure remain the key elements to be taken into account in the loop. There is the need to identify what is missing to close the loop. **Skills** and **scale** are identified as big barriers which are related to human capital and the capacity to invest in machines and equipment, as well as in training. Locally, many steps are still missing in the supply chain, for instance, the spinning part, weaving, and final manufacturing. The core of the discussion revolves around the condition to create business and the degree of agglomerate textile service industry in the local supply chain, for instance, repair textile firms.

Another aspect that is recurrently present in the discussion is the local **regulatory framework** in which the pilot is embedded. Depending on how rigid the regulation and law are, the loop can be prevented or favoured by the local state apparatus and governance arrangements. For instance, the Municipality of Amsterdam is discussing the possibilities for governmental subsidies, namely communal and societal, as a bank for environmental consciousness, in which local authorities might play a role as an initiator or stimulator of the process.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

From the barriers and the goals identified for the "Isolation gowns" use case, a series of actions were listed in chronological order to reach the goal set. This table compiles all the necessary actions, starting by listing the ones performed within the REFLOW project, to reach the desired goal within five years.

During the Reflow project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework Levers	Associated WPs
1. Assess textile streams through qualitative and quantitative methods.	Urban management of assets and material flows	WP3
2. Conduct a workshop for potential ways to transition towards sustainable textile.	Engaging and convening	N/A
3. Map local and national policies related to textiles and CE.	Baseline assessment	WP4
4. Facilitate exchanges between entrepreneurs & sorting companies.	Innovative partnerships	WP4
5. Create policies for tracking labels/smart bins implementation.	Legislation and regulation	WP4
6. Develop a platform for Track & Trace.	Data and tech	WP2, WP5
7. Perform LCA assessments of new gowns vs. single-use gowns: special focus on micro-particle shredding, material use, and primary production impacts.	Social, environmental, economic impact assessment & learning	WP3

Post Reflow project

From year 1 to year 2:

8. Reusable gowns have shown to be beneficial on a sustainability level, hence developing a business case.

From year 2 to year 3:

9. Introduce gowns on a smaller scale to pilot their introduction from a logistical point of view.

10. Conduct an inventory of the current production infrastructures and create an assessment to allow the production of 100,000 gowns (~10t of textile).

From year 3 to year 5:

11. Monitor the material flows, then quantify the quantity of material to track KPIs.

12. Implement procurement guidelines and incentives across public healthcare to ensure multi-use.

Critical Actions

In the 12 proposed actions within the timeline, five of them have been further explained and considered critical for the efficacy of the REFLOW project:

Figure 17: Critical actions co-identified for the Circular Isolation Gowns solution with Amsterdam pilot to achieve 5-year goal

LCA Assessment

This action on the timeline is the critical action of **performing LCA assessments of new gowns vs. single-use gowns** that further implements the impact assessment done in Reflow. To make an educated

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

decision on the adequate replacement of the disposable gowns, it is critical to assess the entire life cycle of each product while prioritising the impacts of micro-particle shredding, material use, and primary production. To perform a rigorous LCA, all the available data on the impacts (e.g. CO₂ emissions, water depletion, land use) must be collected for all production (e.g. virgin fibres), use phase, and end-of-life stages. To assess the use phase impacts of the reusable gowns in the specific local context, periodic assessments can be conducted with the pilot and with key stakeholders (e.g. Municipality of Amsterdam, CleanLease, Tanatex¹⁹). Those can help assess the minimum useful life the reusable gowns must have to surpass disposable gowns in terms of impacts. To facilitate the assessments, the planning, and the monitoring of the use of reusable gowns, databases must be developed and be paired with smart monitoring technologies. Based on these key activities listed, the main levers of implementation required consist of baseline assessment, data and technology and prototyping/ experimenting.

Strengthen Business Case

The following action consists of the business case development. As mentioned above, it is paramount for the success of this solution to present competitive financial advantages when compared to disposable gowns. The pilot highlighted the possibility of implementing the gowns as a service in healthcare institutions in the city. This specific business model will need to be subjected to an evaluation to draw the advantages and disadvantages of not having ownership of the textiles. Moreover, in any case, available subsidies from local governments or organisations to avoid disposable textiles must be researched and considered and a detailed comparative pricing analysis will have to be conducted. After the implementation in one location, a clear roadmap should be built to use as a proof of concept and encourage other healthcare institutions to follow. As part of the MRA roadmap, environmental bodies and governments, ABN-Amro²⁰, Amsterdam Economic Board, or Metabolic can act as key stakeholders to leverage capacity building, prototyping/ experimenting, and public procurement in healthcare institutions.

Small scale pilot

The following critical action, the ninth action from the timeline, consists of the introduction of gowns on a smaller scale (i.e. pilot) and the evaluation of the logistics. A total of 3,000 reusable cotton gowns will be made by Makers Unite and introduced. Frequent feedback will be collected on the ease of use, comfort, and logistics and a special focus will be placed on assessing if they can easily integrate the hospital's workflow without compromising efficiency. At the end of their useful life, the reusable gowns will be mechanically recycled locally. Once again, this action requires leveraging prototyping and experimenting for better insights on the solution.

Scale up

The tenth action along the Backcasting timeline and last critical actions refers to the scaling up of the solution to allow the production of 100,000 gowns (~10t of textile). The Amsterdam pilot has pointed out that an inventory of the current local production infrastructures would first be required. The full value chain mapping exercise will most likely currently involve manufacturers outside of the Netherlands (e.g. Belgium, Portugal, Spain, Italy), which will also give an insight to the pilot on the potential technologies to be implemented

¹⁹ <https://tanatexchemicals.com>

²⁰ <https://www.abnamro.nl>

locally, including REFLOW OS. The same stakeholders as for the smaller scale prototype will be involved and each of their scaling capabilities will be evaluated (e.g. CleanLease, Makers Unite, REBLEND²¹).

Critical dependencies

The 'Isolation gowns' use case, as it is described currently, highly relies on the capability of local stakeholders to provide services and to individually scale up their operations. In the case of Clean Lease, a key partner for the service offering of gowns as-a-service, scaling up their laundry operations should not be a problem. However, to minimise the risks, other service providers should be identified and incorporated within the healthcare institutions workflow. On the other hand, Makers Unite and REBLEND, the local producer of reusable gowns and the textile manufacturer respectively, might have some more difficulties to scale up their operations due to capacity and financial needs. It would then be critical to already approach local gowns producers and textile manufacturers to be involved in the solution.

Impact

The impacts related to the replacement of single-use isolation gowns by reusable ones are covered in detail in the deliverables D7.5, D1.5, and D3.3. In those, the business models, the social return on investments, and the environmental impacts are respectively described. In order to calculate the environmental impacts of this specific use case, a quantitative scaling factor was determined. The factor is aligned with the pilot's goal to replace 5,000,000 gowns by 5,000 reusable ones.

3. BERLIN PILOT

3.1 Pilot Introduction

The REFLOW Berlin Pilot focuses on wastewater heat recovery as a means to guide the city towards climate neutral heating. Wastewater heat is generated as a by-product of water use in industrial processes, and in the everyday domestic life of citizens. Wastewater produced as a result of such processes often retains large amounts of thermal energy, but much of this heat potential is lost to the sewer system. In order to better utilise this resource, the Berlin Pilot seeks to map the potential of wastewater and related waste heat for its efficient recovery, to be further matched with the demand for heat in the city. Greater awareness of this under-utilised energy source is an important component of a successful wastewater heat circular strategy, and the Berlin Pilot aims to increase awareness. From a strategic point of view, the Berlin Pilot has been working on the development of a marketable solution, and on the development of wastewater heat. These are being considered as part of a robust, sustainable business model which will drive implementation across Berlin and other municipalities.

²¹ <https://www.reblend.nl/en/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

The Berlin consortium is composed of four key actors. The first partner, Berliner Wasserbetriebe²² is the sole operator of the sewer network and has the role to be opened to new offers as an energy supplier. The second, Prototypes for Europe²³, act as technology transfer experts responsible for coordination, control, and future of the project. The third one, Fraunhofer Fokus²⁴, has the role of securing software systems for the public sector, and finally, the last, MCS DATALABS²⁵ are experts in databases and are responsible for the processing of data and the backend of the application.

3.2 Ecosystem Mapping

The Circular Loops Diagram exercise allowed the Pilot to identify several areas of opportunity for circular heating loops, as well as for biological loops that constitute the ground for present and future interventions. The diagram depicts what circularity loops the pilots are working on in relation to specific use cases developed through REFLOW activities. It highlights several closed loops for reuse and recovery both for present and future purposes. The multiple loops connect the different levels of stakeholders and the relevant ones are identified.

²² <https://www.bwb.de/de/index.php>

²³ <https://www.prototypes.berlin/>

²⁴ <https://www.fokus.fraunhofer.de/en>

²⁵ <https://mcs-datalabs.com/>

Figure 18: Berlin's Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3

Four circular loops have been identified regarding heat waste and its use:

Recovery	Recover wastewater heat (which is now under-utilised heat) for service providers such as energy and heat providers
Re-use/Re-distribute	Within consumers, the redistribution of heat could happen from one property to another
Re-use/Re-distribute	Redirection of excess heat from retail service providers towards other industries with heat requirement (e.g server farms to parking/local heating grid)
Refurbish/Remanufacture	Refurbishment of city infrastructure and building utilities for better uptake of circular heat

Six potential future loops were identified in relation to the biological nutrient cycle of water:

Regeneration	Improving the quality of the water (removing ammonia) - thus avoiding eutrophication. In order to regenerate a new material resource (water) from the wastewater collection centre
Cascade	Connecting the (waste) water from the collection centre to the city infrastructure facility by improving the value of materials recovered from wastewater: carbon recovery in the form of PHA - could be used for bioplastics and phosphorus and nitrogen could become a base for fertilisers
Extraction of Feedstock	Nutrient could be recovered from wastewater from the collection centre and generate new materials
Biogas	The wastewater collected could be used for the production of biogas as part of an energy recovery system and benefit retailers of complementary energy sources (e.g. Solar, hydro)
Regeneration	Consumers could benefit from wastewater from the collection centre by decentralising nature-based water filtration technologies (like helophyte filters) positioned through urban planning
Recovery	The collected wastewater could feed into urban hydropower system for retailers of complementary energy sources (e.g. Solar, hydro) to benefit from it

The Circular Loops Diagram helped identify many of the possibilities for heat waste recovery and highlight new possible circular flows. Given the lack of data regarding the utilisation of wastewater heat in contrast with the possibilities highlighted during the Circular Loops Diagram workshops, the Berlin solution guarantees a strong step towards future implementation of circular solutions while creating strong awareness and tangible data around the possible concrete reuse of wastewater heat.

3.3 Selected Use Cases

3.3.1 Wastewater Heat Radar

Introduction of the use case

The Berlin Pilot has focussed on wastewater heat. The availability of data is a main barrier to the utilisation of waste heat in general, and specifically the utilisation of wastewater heat. BWB aims to address this by providing an application/dashboard that maps the potential of wastewater heat. This platform maps waste (water) heat supply and demand, and creates matches between suppliers and users. The solution bridges the gap between supply and demand by way of matchmaking and addresses the lack of overview of supply and demand at municipal/city level,

thus increasing both the awareness of the potential of wastewater heat, but also contributing to its recovery. This allows buildings in which heat recovery can take place to reduce their energy costs, and improve their sustainability profile.

The digital layer consists of a dynamic web application that maps waste heat potential with consumers depending on the water pipe infrastructure, which should be at least partly automated. While the organisational platform functions as a quasi-agency that addresses different groups of actors, the implementation of waste heat technologies includes reference projects in nearby districts of the city. Therefore, the Berlin Pilot has broadly discussed how to unlock and hack the metabolic potential of water in the urban environment by facilitating the use of waste heat in the built environment, and coupling it efficiently with complementary energy and water sources.

Amongst many European civic-level decision-makers, wastewater heat utilisation is considered a valid option for circular heating systems. In Germany, renewable energy and waste heat have become priorities for local and central governments. Although all buildings generate wastewater heat, it is nonetheless challenging for a building to utilise the wastewater heat it generates, which is why the supply and demand based matchmaking platform demonstrates the potential of the city in reaching its circular heating goals.

Within the REFLOW timeline, the Berlin pilot has mapped the Berlin metropolitan region wastewater heat potential through an open source web application in the style of a radar (Figure 17). This application is targeted to urban planners, engineers and architects, and property developers to use the potential wastewater heat as an energy source in buildings and infrastructures. On the database, the potential wastewater heat recovered (extraction power and heating load) can be assessed for different addresses and sites can be compared with one another (Figure 18).

Figure 19: Screenshot from the Berlin Wastewater Heat Radar interface showing an area with available data

Figure 20: Screenshot from the Berlin Wastewater Heat Radar interface showing the estimation of extraction power vs. heating load with radius function

Description of the 5 years goal

The five-year goal is strictly connected to the scalability factors within the proposed time frame. The attainable goal is to provide a digital and organisational platform for optimising the use of waste-heat via the medium of water as a means of reducing the CO₂-footprint of properties in metropolitan areas.

What are the barriers to this goal?

A significant barrier to achieving this goal is the lack of awareness and available information/ data about the supply of, and demand for, wastewater heat. As a result, occupiers/ owners of buildings are unaware of the potential. Buildings which are downstream from heat generation have potential to capture wastewater heat. The identification of such high-potential buildings is key, and this is dependent on a range of factors, including current energy sources and the size of the building. Even given similar profiles, demand for wastewater heating is not equal across different buildings. Because of the cost of deployment of equipment, priority should be given to buildings which have a high enough energy consumption to utilise wastewater heat to full potential. This avoids the installation of several types of capture equipment for houses that only have limited capacity for use of the equipment.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

This table compiles an initial set of necessary actions within the use case Wastewater Heat Radar to reach the desired goal within five years.

During the Reflow project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework Levers	Associated WPs
1. Strategic foundation developed for the software based on baseline assessments of similar tools and targeted stakeholders.	Data and Tech and Baseline Assessments	WP2 and WP5
2. Outreach campaign was conducted about wastewater heat through various media.	Communication and Awareness raising	WP7
3. Prototype of the wastewater heat radar platform developed.	Data and Tech and Prototyping and experimentation	WP5
4. Monitoring of wastewater heat is conducted and enabled with the collection of prototype data.	Data and Tech	N/A
5. Business models are developed for the monitoring platform.	Fiscal measures and Public procurement	WP7

Post-Reflow project

From year 1 to year 2:

6. Assess and quantify data from the prototype for better evaluation of wastewater heat

7. Apply the wastewater heat recovery technology as a functional prototype with the municipal water agency (BWB) in Berlin, with partners implementing the tech in their infrastructure

8. Elaborate a replication strategy - taking inputs from the implementation on what works and what doesn't; and identify suitable cities for replication

9. Identify new potential partners, utilities, and stakeholders across the different cities

10. Contact potential partners (engineers, water utilities, developers) in other cities and build working relationships with the respective municipalities

From year 2 to year 3:

11. Organise initiatives and discussions with industry focus groups (2-6 organisations)

12. Conduct surveys and indications of interest in targeted cities - leading to actual implementation of wastewater recovery infrastructures

From year 3 to year 5:

13. Identification of how to create monetary flow with the replication of the application from expressions of interest

14. Spread further awareness to city networks and create curiosity through dissemination and requests

Critical Actions

Along the Backcasting timeline, 14 actions were identified as necessary to the achievement of the 5-year goal for the elimination of plastic food packaging. In order to substantiate the transformative potential of the goal, out of the total list of actions, five critical actions have been further expanded with the pilots and the key sub-actions and relevant stakeholders were highlighted.

Figure 21: Critical actions co-identified for the wastewater reuse solution with Berlin pilot to achieve 5-year goal

Replication Strategy

The first critical action within the timeline refers to the potential replication strategy of the wastewater heat radar which will be elaborated by taking the inputs from implementation in Berlin on what worked well and what is missing (*prototyping and experimentation* lever). The identified key sub-actions to be carried out are the elaboration of a city network for better outreach, the ideal partner for which has been currently identified as ICLEI²⁶ (*innovative partnerships* lever). Inputs need to be gathered on the needs of other cities (*baseline assessment* lever). A strategy must then be elaborated, based on the needs, in order to implement this technology elsewhere and assure a degree of replicability (*roadmap and strategies* lever). The essential stakeholders for this

²⁶ <https://iclei.org/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

action have been identified as Prototypes for Europe, Fraunhofer Fokus, ICLEI and city-based organisations which are in charge of shaping the energy strategy of a metropolitan area (e.g. Berlin Energy Agency). These stakeholders will ideally be connected to a set of “local heroes” for technological and consultative support.

Partnership Identification

The following action builds on the replication strategy elaborated and focuses on identifying and contacting the potential partners, utilities, and stakeholders across different cities to create formal and informal partnerships for the use of the radar. The key sub-actions gravitate around the identification of best-suited partners for implementation, including developers (*baseline assessment and innovative partnerships* lever) and around the demonstration of the app to show the data required and how it can be implemented in other cities (*data and tech and capacity building* levers). This step also requires developing working relationships with municipalities of different cities for public projects, and finding the needs and specific selling points for cities to make the solution more attractive (*innovative partnerships and fiscal measures* levers). The principal stakeholders are Prototypes for Europe, Berliner Wasserbetriebe (with equivalents across different cities), a cities network (ICLEI) for the connection with other city municipalities and lastly the local energy agencies in different cities as audience for the needs assessment.

Network Building

This action immediately follows the previous critical action and pertains to network building with the identified cities. After the identification of an array of key partners, initiatives and discussions need to be organised with industry focus groups in each city, with approximately six to ten organisations participating (e.g. cities’ municipal water and energy utilities, engineering firms, real estate developers and other industry leaders) (*engaging and convening and innovative partnerships* levers). The key sub-actions will be identifying the focus groups driving change in each city, facilitating the connection between them, and hosting the focus groups. This series of sub-actions can first be led by a common parent organisation (e.g. tbd) to later be owned by an organisation in each city. The aim of these focus group discussions will be to recognize potential barriers and plan actions to overcome them (i.e. cultural, different budgets/timelines, legislation) (*roadmap and strategies* lever). Vattenfall²⁷, which has a presence across the EU as one of EU’s largest producers and retailers of electricity and heat, could be a unifying entity in all city focus group discussions.

Expression of interest

The next critical action consists of conducting surveys and requesting for an expression of interest in targeted cities, which will be leading to actual implementation. The key sub-actions are facilitating the expression of interest from other cities for future implementation; the identification of potential new regulations in cities (*baseline assessment* lever); and the creation of an advocacy campaign for the implementation of new regulations where needed (*legislation and regulation and awareness raising* levers). This action will involve

²⁷ <https://group.vattenfall.com/>

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

creating an overview of national/local subsidies for sustainable actions in every location, as implementations will require funding either locally or at national or regional level (*baseline assessment and fiscal measures lever*). Another potential avenue to be assessed is the EU funding for replication or scaling of H2020 projects, for which a proposal and consortium will have to be built in the near future (*fiscal measures and innovative partnership levers*). The main stakeholders to be involved in this critical action will be local actors involved in the focus groups in every city to fill the Expression of Interest (e.g. municipal water management agencies, municipal water utilities, operator companies, technology providers, engineering firms, real estate developers, etc.); financial institutions (national/regional bodies for subsidies or the EC), ICLEI for facilitating the connections needed for the Eol, and Prototypes for Europe to facilitate a consortium for future EC proposals.

Identify monetary flow

The last action on the timeline marked as critical is the identification of the means to create monetary flow from expressions of interest of European cities in the long term. After providing the tool for the assessment of potential high wastewater heat sites in cities, the Berlin pilot has thought of expanding their service offering by potentially forming two new ventures (*roadmap and strategies lever*). The first potential venture would be to offer waste heat infrastructure as a service, and the second would be to partner with an engineering/construction company to supply and offer the installation of wastewater heat hardware (*innovative partnership lever*). To support these ventures, awareness or marketing campaigns will be required as well through the local media (*awareness raising and communication lever*). The future stakeholder will be the two ventures and their comprising partners, the municipal water management agencies of identified cities for collaborating with the venture creating “infrastructure as a service”, and the local entities that manufacture wastewater hardware.

Critical dependencies

One of the critical dependencies to be taken into account in the future for the replication of the wastewater heat radar system is the European funding landscape for replication of the Horizon 2020 project. Hence, there is a need to identify major sources of funding, and to change the business model, by offering different services. Last but not least, the partnership with ICLEI as a key partner to establish the solution in multiple cities remains one of the critical dependencies to be tackled. Specifically, the Pilot seeks to identify other multi-cities partner/organisations (e.g. Prototypes for Europe), by developing relationships with multiple organisations with relations to other cities, as well as a partner with equipment suppliers instead.

Impacts

The impacts related to the development of the wastewater heat platform are covered in detail in four upcoming REFLOW deliverables. The business models (D7.5), the social return on investments (D1.5), the governance model (D4.4) and the environmental impacts (D3.3) of the use case are respectively described in the listed deliverables.

In order to calculate the environmental impacts of this specific use case, BWB has estimated the potential CO2 reductions based on the scaling of wastewater heat installations across the city of Berlin. The assumption is that

the Wastewater Heat Radar leads to a full usage of the technical exploitable wastewater heat potential in Berlin on a long-term perspective. A detailed overview of the calculations will be published in the upcoming D3.3.

Conclusion

Focusing on energy consumption, one of the largest uses in Germany is residential heating. Much of the energy transition and the use of wastewater heat back into the energy streams requires a change in behaviour, consumption, and production across politicians, planners, other decision-making bodies and citizens. The push for sustainable energy transitions and climate protection in Germany and the EU highlights wastewater heat potential as a key resource to tackle this aim.

The Berlin Pilot has also reflected on next steps. For instance, the local ecosystem is currently composed of stakeholders in particular around waste heat which is all based across Europe. This network is usually dominated by one or a few public utility companies (such as BWB) and companies that generate or consume waste heat. At the moment the issue of waste heat remains overlooked by civil society. Hence, raising awareness amongst citizens is a crucial factor for the realisation of the project. By doing so, access to properties and tools for citizens are facilitated and equipped with waste heat technology in a particularly tangible way for scaling up the project.

4. CLUJ PILOT

4.1 Pilot Introduction

The goal of the REFLOW Cluj-Napoca pilot is the improvement of the energy efficiency of public and residential buildings across the city. The pilot aims, within the REFLOW project, to assess the impact of the current measures taken to date by the city on the energy efficiency of selected buildings and to involve local stakeholders in implementing these measures. In parallel, the pilot hopes to stimulate different actors within the ecosystem to propose new innovative ideas regarding the integration of renewable energy sources while educating them on the city's circular economy strategy.

The Cluj-Napoca REFLOW Consortium is composed of the Municipality of Cluj-Napoca²⁸, Aries Transilvania²⁹ and the National Institute for Research and Development of Isotopic and Molecular Technologies³⁰ (ITIM).

While stakeholders involved in the project reach other branches of the ecosystem, the main collaborators are coordinated by the Municipality and their ideas are part of the co-creation of policy at a local level. Specifically, Aries Transilvania is in charge of mapping the existing energy suppliers, and is also responsible for the

²⁸ <https://primariaclujnapoca.ro>

²⁹ <https://aries-transilvania.ro/en/>

³⁰ <http://ro.itim-cj.ro>

dissemination of the existing information and knowledge. The ITIM is responsible for developing research in the field of energy efficiency. The purpose of this is to bring together stakeholders that can contribute to the development of new ideas, and the testing of these within the pilot city.

4.2 Ecosystem mapping

The ecosystem mapping exercise helped the pilot map possible activities that would increase energy efficiency within the city and to bring the system to a more circular state. The Circular Loops Diagram built identifies those future loops ranging from shifting energy sources to locally retrofit buildings. The scale and level of implementation and resources required to pursue each of those loops vary largely while covering a large spectrum of energy related circular activities.

Within the scope of REFLOW, the pilot has decided to pursue the installation of Retrofit Kits inside municipality-owned buildings to reduce the consumption of electricity and increase efficiency. The following diagram highlights the use case selected while maintaining the future loops as a reference for greater impact and more radical changes.

Figure 22: Cluj-Napoca’s Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3

As previously mentioned, the loops identified in this latest version of the Circular Loops Diagram can be divided into existing loops, which have been conducted within the REFLOW project, and future loops that show potential for further improvement on the city’s energy and electricity consumption.

The shorter term loop identified that has been initiated during REFLOW is the following:

Reduce/ Maintain/ Prolong/ Share	Creation of a circular connection between the consumer and user. The Retrofit Kit solution provided by the local supplier Servelect SRL ³¹ and RF Meters ³² helps reduce the energy use of retrofitted buildings. Further, it facilitates the collection of usage data with the purpose of informing energy procurement and analysis.
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Within the possible future loops, Cluj-Napoca addresses the production and integration of renewable energies (biomass, hydro, wind). These natural cycles allow for the potential of the sustainable management and renewal of biological resources. The identified loop connection for these use cases mainly creates possibilities to reuse discarded material and translate it into raw materials such as:

Recycle/ Reuse	Heat waste could be recovered from public buildings for the purpose of reuse and redistribution
Refurbish/ Remanufacture	For refurbishment towards energy efficiency, a connection can be established between the city’s public buildings and manufacturers for insulation systems. This loop identifies the opportunity for design towards circularity of insulation material.

3.3 Selected use cases

3.3.1 Retrofit Kit

Introduction of the use case

In the Deliverable D3.2, the Energy Flow Assessment (EFA) identified electricity consumption as the main contributor of CO2 emissions from Cluj-Napoca’s public buildings. The two recommended areas of focus consisted of increasing the energy efficiency of public buildings and assets and to prepare Cluj-Napoca for a future decentralised, renewable energy system. The pilot has decided to pursue the first focus area and increase the energy efficiency in local public schools with the installation of a Retrofit Kit.

³¹ <https://servelect.ro/en/>

³² <https://www.rf-meters.com>

The Retrofit Kit is aimed at reducing energy consumption where it is installed. The core is to install the Retrofit Kit solution which allows for an estimated 15% reduction of electricity consumption. The Retrofit Kit is a combination of five components: smart sockets, electric panels, motion sensors, lighting fixtures and a smart metering system. The novelty does not lie in the individual components per se, but rather in the way they are combined into a package. The installation of external hardware was seen as an alternative to costly renovation in existing buildings to reduce electricity consumption.

Additionally, the pilot explored the possibility of including a dashboard to give an overview of energy consumption in the building along with recommendations. The reasoning behind this is to enable targeted interventions for additional energy savings and circular behaviour regarding energy consumption. .

To achieve the development of the Retrofit Kit, the pilot has carried out a collaborative process between local partners and the ecosystem in the design of the solution. The pilot hosted a series of stakeholder mapping meetings where the pilot team identified an important number of actors that were willing to contribute to the development of an innovative, yet affordable solution to increase energy efficiency. Cluj-Napoca then invited these actors to a series of meetings (in a brainstorm-like format) to identify the best pathway for action. The meetings concluded that the pilot would install a hardware-software package (consisting of smart sockets, LED lighting system, light and movement sensors (Figure 21), new electric panels and connections and a smart metering system + monitoring software) in the dormitory of the “Energetic” Highschool in Cluj-Napoca. In February 2021, Cluj-Napoca proceeded to the installation of the Kit in the dormitory which consisted in its entirety of: 145 LED lighting fixtures, 40 motion sensors, six electrical panels, 16 smart wall sockets, 10 mono-phase digital metres, and 10 radio communicators. The objective of this use case seeks to support the energy transition in Cluj-Napoca through retrofitting infrastructure and energy data collection and interpretation

Figure 23: Light and movement sensors

Description of the 5 years goal

The attainable 5 years goal for the selected use case is to decrease electricity consumption by a minimum of 15% in the buildings where the Retrofit kit is applied within one year of installation; and to deploy it in public buildings based on demand from the municipality to support an increase in energy efficiency in its buildings.

What are the barriers to this goal?

When visualising the 5-years goal identified, a list of barriers were raised with the pilot. Those pertain to different spheres, such as behavioural, regulatory, and financial. From a **behavioural perspective**, people who work in real estate and construction companies are not easily inclined to change their work process, and are reluctant to accept the transition. The Municipality itself currently faces financial challenges with the **cost of scaling** of about 20,000 euros per building (depending on the type).

To address the behavioural and financial challenges, one of the potential solutions is to increase awareness about energy consumption amongst different local communities. In terms of legislation, it is important to include the energy retrofit into building regulations and make accessible guidelines for citizens and building developers.

There is also an **information barrier** as there are many variables to consider during any energy consumption analysis, and this causality is hard to prove. As one example, the pandemic, which drastically increased remote working, led to lower use of office buildings, providing a skewed baseline for the assessment. This discrepancy can affect the actual outcomes of the solution and make it more difficult to get the buy-in from critical actors.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

To attain the goal described above, the main barriers must be overcome, which leads to a series of eighteen actions required for the success of the pilot. The table below indicates in chronological order a set of actions required to reach the attainable goal.

During Reflow project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework levers	Associated WPs
1. Local collaboration with Technical University to gather a catalogue of all relevant projects in the city	Baseline Assessment	WP1
2. Conduct workshops on solutions regarding fitting and other measures that increase energy efficiency	Engaging and Convening	N/A
3. Engaging the IT community to develop an app for monitoring energy consumption.	Data and Tech	W5, WP2
4. Procure and pilot the Retrofit Kit (hardware) in a school dormitory.	Prototyping and experimentation	W5, WP2
5. Train employees to use the Retrofit Kit with the monitoring app.	Capacity Building	WP6
6. Perform an impact analysis on the energy use of the pilot.	Social, environmental, economic impact assessment	WP1

7. Produce a study report on energy consumption and create an open database.	Communication	WP4
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Post Reflow project:

From year 1 to year 2:

- 8. Have the user of the building fill in surveys to assess the qualitative and quantitative performance of retrofitting
- 9. Use the data gathered for sending a message about circular economy scenarios and raising awareness of Cluj's citizens
- 10. Create a promotional package for the Retrofit Kit
- 11. Perform an eligibility assessment of the public buildings to use the Retrofit Kit
- 12. Assess methods to finance the installation of the Retrofit Kits in public buildings
- 13. Application for EU funding for the replication of the Retrofit Kits
- 14. Introduce a financing scheme to facilitate the installation in more buildings

From year 3 to year 5:

- 15. Provide technical training to the main users of the retrofitted buildings
- 16. Purchase and install the Retrofit Kits in multiple public buildings in Cluj
- 17. Facilitate discussions between users and consumers of the buildings and the municipality to raise awareness about monitoring energy savings
- 18. Create an app/ visualisation website to educate and raise awareness of the users and to show results

Critical Actions

Some actions have been identified as critical (highlighted above) and have been detailed with levers and the stakeholder ecosystem required for the action.

Figure 24: Critical actions co-identified for the Retrofit Kit solution with Cluj pilot to achieve 5-year goal

In the array of actions listed above, the five crucial steps identified will happen after the conclusion of the three years of REFLOW. These have been further discussed with the pilot as they will be key in the achievement of the 5-years goal.

Performance review

The first critical action identified pertains to the performance review. This action aims to understand the use of the building where the Retrofit Kit is installed. The environmental, social, and financial impacts, and how the users' behaviour interacts with the energy consumption will be assessed with the help of ARIES Transalvania. To do this, qualitative surveys will be sent by the Municipality to relevant stakeholders, such as the users and administrators of the school dormitory, and data will be collected to provide a clear quantitative picture (*engaging and convening & baseline assessment levers*).

Awareness raising

This critical action refers to the use of the collected data to send a message about circular economy scenarios and raise awareness about the future among Cluj citizens. The key sub-actions required to achieve this underline the importance of generating a strong message and creating a public campaign for the general notion of circularity using the Retrofit Kit as an emblematic case and other several outputs (*communication, and awareness raising levers*) are the key levers of implementation for this task. The stakeholders' ecosystem will solicit actors such as public institutions but also citizens (e.g. CIIC, Centre for Citizens' Innovation and Creativity)³³, companies interested in building similar software and hardware, and other private sector firms.

Financing

Financing is critical for the replication of the solution across other public buildings in Cluj-Napoca. Current financing methods will have to be critically assessed, including EU funding. The pilot has identified EU calls for funding as one of the most achievable sources of funds to scale the solution within the city, and has also identified the possibility to find subsidies for the hardware (*economic and financial incentives levers*).

Kits installation

After having found the required financing and published public tenders to purchase the Retrofit Kits, the next critical step will be to proceed with the installation in the selected public buildings. Strategically, the buildings with the most energy consumption should initially be targeted and used as a proof of concept. Public procurement guidelines can act as a key lever to accelerate the purchase of the kits, where the Municipality of Cluj and its purchasing department take charge of the urban management of assets.

App creation

Finally, to best educate and raise awareness of the users, an app or a visualisation website will be created. The consumption over-time, the building information (e.g. year of construction), and the reduction impacts are data that will be displayed on a map-based dashboard (*Engaging and convening, raising awareness, and using data and technology levers*). The Fraunhofer - Engineering Institute³⁴, that has capabilities in app and website development and that is already working with the pilot, would be a key stakeholder to develop this asset.

Critical dependencies

An important dependency raised while listing the actions required to scale up the solution with the pilot is the needs for EU funding. As of now, the pilot has not yet identified other possible sources of funding to install the Retrofit Kits in other municipal buildings. This makes the replicability of the solution extremely fragile and puts a lot of risks on the obtention of this funding. As it was listed above, identifying financing methods is key, and a more diversified portfolio of funders should already be developed.

³³ <https://primariaclujnapoca.ro/cetateni/centrul-de-inovare-si-imaginatie-civica/>

³⁴ <https://www.iao.fraunhofer.de/en.html>

An alternative to finding external funding would be to use public resources which would not be ideal for the pilot.

One of the main critical dependencies widely discussed by the pilot concerns the relation between the Municipality of Cluj-Napoca and the energy distributor firms. The pilot has sought to find a way to accommodate the Municipality's demand in order to get access to its energy consumption data, by doing so they do not intend to cause any extra cost to the distributor company.

Impacts

The impacts related to the installation of the Retrofit Kits are covered in detail in the upcoming REFLOW deliverables. The business models (D7.5), the social return on investments (D1.5), and the environmental impacts (D3.3) of the use case are respectively described in the listed deliverables.

In order to calculate the environmental impacts of this specific use case, a quantitative scaling factor was determined through the T5.3 exercise. This factor is aligned with the pilot's goal to reduce the electricity consumption by 15% in 15% of the municipal buildings, which should be achieved within a 5-years period.

5. MILAN PILOT

5.1 Pilot Introduction

The REFLOW Milan Pilot focuses on supporting the transition to a circular food system. It does this by connecting fundamental actors involved in the tracking and distribution of food throughout the city. The Milan Pilot initiated a series of activities around co-creation, co-design, and co-production to facilitate a systematic transition of the Milanese urban food system to a circular model for agrifood products, such as fruit, vegetables, cereals, meat, fish, and dairy.

To make this systemic change possible, the Milan pilot needed to develop a new way of operating within the value chain based on the tracking of materials and processes connected to the key players of the urban food system. To set the stage for this change, the Milan pilot's development pathway was founded on connecting a multitude of different actors in the urban food system, including large municipal enterprises, wholesalers, universities (Polimi³⁵), FabLabs (WeMake³⁶, OpenDot³⁷, Polifactory³⁸), and makerspaces, and allowing for possible paths of circular and social innovations to emerge from these collaborations. In the co-creation phase, workshops with key actors in the urban food system were undertaken, and led to the co-creation of scenarios that would set clear directions for all

³⁵ <https://www.polimi.it/en/>

³⁶ <https://wemake.cc/>

³⁷ <https://www.opendotlab.it/>

³⁸ <https://www.polifactory.polimi.it/en/>

pilot activities and interventions. These scenarios underwent further co-development with relevant stakeholders, and led to the definition of concrete actions and tangible outputs of the Milan pilot. In practice, these interventions in the material flow are tested at different scales, looking at the flow through Milan's main food wholesale market, SoGeMi³⁹, and the city's 23 covered municipal markets.

Overall, two concrete and actionable axes became the focal points of the pilot and were integrated into an overarching roadmap for the last year of REFLOW and beyond.

- *Food waste prevention and reduction in wholesaling markets.*
- *Tracking food flows across local supply chains.*

The full overview of activities of Milan pilots can be found in REFLOW Deliverable 1.4. These activities description will also be updated in the upcoming REFLOW Deliverable 1.5.

5.2 Ecosystem mapping

Throughout the duration of the REFLOW project, numerous activities have been carried out by the pilot in order to engage and support the transformation in the Milan pilot region which have been reflected and analysed in T5.3 using the Circular Loops Diagram. The Circular Loops Diagram reflects the Milan Pilot's focus on circularity, and in particular, the actions required to improve circular flow with the identified and involved actors.

³⁹ <https://www.sogemispa.it/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

Figure 25: Milan's Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3

Since the REFLOW Milan Pilot tackles an organic material (food waste), this enabled the exploration of loops revolving around renewable materials within the Circular Loops Diagram. This in turn facilitated the Milan Pilot's identification of possible use cases, be it the cascading of organic resources through re-use, regeneration of resources, the extraction of feedstocks, and/or anaerobic digestion. Each of these cycles offer future opportunities for the Milan Pilot. Overall, this exercise has highlighted an important need and therefore opportunity in terms of the reuse and redistribution of organic resources. Unsaleable, but still edible, products from markets are redistributed to NGOs and organisations at city and metropolitan levels who operate within *distribution, and service provider/retail*. Additionally, this exploration led to the question of logistics, a critical component of any supply chain. Tracking is especially important for circular supply chains, where food must be tracked throughout the different supply chains to both provide transparency and help reduce waste. As a result, the Circular Loops Diagram yielded two main loops as the main focus of the pilot's roadmap development for the last year of REFLOW and beyond: food waste reuse/re-distribution and food flow tracking (logistics).

By selecting these two use cases, the Milan Pilot can work concretely towards its goals of establishing a food recovery protocol deployed across all wholesale and covered markets in Milan with the local NGO, RECUP. And of deploying a food tracing dashboard in Milan which extends from local producers to SoGeMi, to specific covered markets (Farm to Fork) such as the Morsenchio Municipal Market.

Foody Zero Waste

Cascade (Re-use/Re-distribute)	(Edible) Food Waste is recovered by RECUP at the wholesaling stage (Part Manufacturer) in SoGeMi markets and re-channeled towards service providers (in this case charities) to offer food to local populations in need.
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Food Market 4.0

Distribution (Logistics):	Food Market 4.0 Dashboard includes inventory tracking, logistics planning, and controlling for the inbound and outbound of fruit and vegetables flowing through the municipal markets.
Cascade (Re-use/Re-distribute) Future loop	The tracking component of this solution also has the possibility of being connected to the Foody Zero Waste solution which allows for the further reduction of food waste.

Future loops

Regeneration	Nutrient for fruit and vegetables through a <i>regeneration</i> : composting of (inedible) organic waste to return the nutrients to the earth
Extraction of feedstock	Feedstock for polymers through the <i>extraction of feedstock</i> for biopolymers and fertilisers.
Anaerobic digestion	Biogas through <i>anaerobic digestion</i> of inedible food waste

5.3 Selected use cases

The REFLOW Milan Pilot focused on the two use cases focused on the ‘reuse’ and ‘redistribution’ of resources: Foody Zero Waste, and Food Market 4.0.

5.3.1 Foody Zero Waste

Introduction of the use case

The use case focuses on the recovery of unsold food within the Foody Hub market, managed by SoGeMi. The use case is a collaboration with SoGeMi, RECUP⁴⁰, and other local NGOs, such as the Italian Red Cross⁴¹, and selected wholesalers. The main piloting activities is supported by the NGO RECUP, and uses digital tools –such as BOTTO – to optimise the communication and delivery of surplus food to the network of Milan food associations. As the main outcome of Foody Zero Waste, BOTTO is an interface that allows an automated communication solution (through Telegram) to facilitate the reallocation of surplus fruit and vegetable products made available by SoGeMi wholesalers to selected stakeholders (such as RECUP, Banco Alimentare, etc). Practically, it is a physical device that sends GraphQL calls to the Reflow OS systems dedicated to BOTTO. BOTTO solution helps address the unpredictable supply from markets – i.e. the type and the amount of food which varies greatly and the demand challenges the food recovery organisations face, by having a quick and real-time snapshot of the available food. Moreover, wholesalers do not need to struggle with coordinating their own food supply, as BOTTO allows for these actors to easily display their supply to a range of charity organisations – in this case, the Italian Red Cross during the piloting period – while also easily defining an agreement with them. BOTTO is further described in REFLOW Deliverable D5.4. Finally, Foody Zero Waste allows the wholesalers to reduce waste management expenses and improve their social and environmental sustainability.

The Foody Zero Waste solution was implemented with fruit and vegetable Wholesalers, RECUP and the Italian Red Cross in February 2022 within the SoGeMi market. The BOTTO device was distributed to wholesalers to indicate the food surplus (Figure 24 and 25). The use case output included the testing of the digital solution developed by REFLOW OS, Opendot, and RECUP's own network of food charities.

⁴⁰ <https://associazionerecup.org/>

⁴¹ <https://cri.it/>

Figure 26: BOTTO device

Figure 27: Telegram BOT interacting between wholesalers and organisations

Description of the 5 years goal

The five year goal for Milan Foody Zero Waste is to deploy the food waste recovery protocol, including the BOTTO hardware and software systems across all SoGeMi wholesale markets and Milan’s 23 municipal covered markets, to drastically reduce food waste through optimised re-distribution channels.

What are the barriers to this goal?

In the problem analysis definition, the Milan pilot was able to further elaborate which are the different barriers and challenges to be solved to achieve the five year goal.

Several **logistical barriers** have been identified. The first major logistical barrier to the achievement of the five-year goal concerns the lack of cold-storage facilities for left-over food. In the fast-paced environment of food logistics and in the context of variable supply and demand of recovered food, highly perishable food products need to be stored temporarily to avoid their further degradation and increase the rate of food saved from the trash. A second barrier relates to the heterogeneity of the market waste management system which represents an obstacle to adopting a systematic and shared strategy amongst all the actors involved. Third, an interconnected obstacle is the lack of available space in covered markets - as the food waste recovery protocol is deployed across these municipal markets, the lack of space becomes a challenge due to additional spaces required for sorting and the temporary (cold) storage of recovered food. Finally, food sorting is a time-consuming, manual activity, the pilot is aware of its limitations.

Additionally, some **incentive barriers** have been identified. First, the incentivisation of food waste donation (the transformation of pain to gain) and volunteer management for food redistribution can be challenging, especially at scale, and across organisations, tools, and tracking devices. The incentive structure must be established to

encourage both the participation of wholesalers across SoGeMi markets and food market stalls in covered markets and the volunteers upon which organisations like RECUP depend to redistribute the recovered food. Overall, the development of a business model to build the incentivisation model of RECUP remains a critical challenge to be solved.

Finally, a **technological and financial barrier** identified is the need to scale the manufacturing of BOTTO devices beyond maker-spaces manufacturing capabilities and gather the required financing to do so.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

As previously mentioned, the identified barriers and challenges raised by the local actors have ignited the elaboration of a detailed timeline to scale the pilot’s solution after REFLOW and reach the defined goal. This table compiles, to begin, the key steps achieved within the REFLOW project by the Milan pilot, followed by all the necessary actions within the use case Foody Zero Waste to reach the desired goal in a five year period, the latter having been developed within the Backcasting exercise. Overall, along the Backcasting timeline, 19 actions were identified as necessary to the achievement of the 5-year goal of Foody Zero Waste of deploying the food waste recovery protocol across all wholesaling and covered markets in Milan.

During Reflow project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework levers	Associated WPs
1. Engage with SoGeMi market manager.	Engaging and Convening	WP4
2. Map micro and macro material food flow (inclusive of food waste) across SoGeMi markets.	Urban management of assets and material flows	WP3
3. Map hands-on field research in fruits and vegetable markets to gain real-world understanding of logistics.	Baseline assessment	WP1
4. Conduct a co-creation workshop with Municipal Markets to define an action plan on food waste recovery.	Roadmaps, strategies, action plans	WP1, WP4
5. Create a Co-design lab with SoGeMi/Foody Hub, RECUP, covered markets.	Prototyping and experimentation	WP1
6. Conduct prototyping workshop – BOTTO prototyping and testing in a real world setting.	Prototyping and experimentation	WP2 and WP5
7. Test the communication devices with the pilot group (fruits and veggies wholesaler, RECUP, Red Cross).	Prototyping and experimentation	WP2 and WP5

Post Reflow project

From year 1 to year 2:

8. Create an evaluation of the communication devices. Reduce the overhead of food surplus management with the pilot.

From year 2 to year 3:

9. Deploy the communication device across all wholesalers in SoGeMi markets.

10. Research and identify the main challenges for SoGeMi and covered markets about cold storage and sorting space. Assess feasibility..

11. Rombon market is the first pilot for cold storage

From year 3 to year 5:

12. Design sorting spaces nearby each market or inside each market

13. Conduct research on food recovery business models with incentive structures for wholesaling and covered markets

14. The municipality establishes requirements in terms of management of market (waste management, sorting and storage spaces)

15. Develop an economic and financial plan for each market that include incentive model and new municipal requirements

16. Deploy communal cold storage in So.Ge.Mi

17. Pilot sorting strategies and redistribution logistics with Rombon market and SoGeMi and RECUP

18. Establish a clear partnership between markets and food rescue organisations across markets

19. Deploy communal cold storage across all wholesaling and covered markets in Milan

Critical Actions

Across the 19 actions, several have been identified as critical (highlighted above) and have been detailed with levers and the stakeholder ecosystem required for the action.

Figure 28: Critical actions co-identified for Foody Zero Waste with the Milan pilot to achieve the 5-year goal

In order to substantiate the transformative potential of the selected 5-year goal, 5 critical actions were highlighted by the pilot team, 3 of which were further expanded upon with the pilot team to define the key sub-actions and identified all the relevant stakeholders.

Testing of communication devices

The testing phase is the first critical action highlighted. It pertains to the testing of the BOTTO devices with the participating fruits and vegetables wholesalers (Casa Grande, Galafruit⁴², local producers Consortium) in SoGeMi, RECUP, and the Italian Red Cross to assess how the devices perform in optimising logistics and user preferences. The key sub-actions required consist of testing of communication devices and REFLOW OS to ensure user-friendliness of the communication device and iteratively respond to user preference and on-field performance of the device (*prototyping/experimentation* lever). This sub-action also entails to ensure the smooth integration of BOTTO into the REFLOW OS platform from a software and hardware perspective (*data/tech* lever). The principal stakeholders required were SoGeMi wholesalers, RECUP, the Italian Red Cross, Open Dot, WeMake, and REFLOW OS developers, which all were involved in the testing phase.

Deployment of communication devices across all wholesalers

This action is devoted to the deployment of BOTTO communication devices across all wholesalers in SoGeMi markets. With the goal of expanding the food waste recovery protocol, a key sub-action relates to RECUP becoming a service provider to recover food and re-channel it towards organisations fighting food poverty (*engaging and convening* lever). Another key sub-action is for RECUP to become an educator to display the benefits of these actions to wholesalers, and raise awareness about the possibility to use BOTTO as a user-friendly solution with various level of digital literacy, while SoGeMi must create incentive structures to encourage wholesalers to uptake the device (*awareness raising* and *capacity building* levers). Additionally, a key sub-action relates to creating a long-lasting partnership with OpenDot, the device manufacturer, and gathering the necessary investment to enable scaling the production and purchase of communication devices to supply all wholesalers (*data and tech and fiscal measures* levers). The main stakeholders are RECUP, SoGeMi, OpenDot, the users of the BOTTO devices, and the wholesalers who have yet to uptake the new device.

Scaling to municipal covered markets

The last action reviewed as critical is the scaling of the food waste recovery protocol to Milan municipal covered markets. A key sub-action will focus on identifying the needs of the different food stalls across the markets in terms of food waste logistics and management (*baseline assessment and engaging and convening* levers). Secondly, another key sub-action will involve raising awareness about the food waste recovery protocol supported by BOTTO communication devices and successfully implemented at the wholesale level (SoGeMi markets) (*awareness raising* lever). To cover the communication needs for each vendor in the 23 covered markets, securing financing will be another key sub-action, to build the required manufacturing capabilities for the hardware production and the maintenance capabilities for the software (*fiscal measures* lever). Finally, the different management models of the markets must be assessed for each covered market, to facilitate the integration of the food waste recovery protocol within each of them. This step can be facilitated by the Municipality of Milan as it can support the visioning exercise required to integrate the food waste recovery protocol into existing management models.

⁴² <https://galafruit.net/en/>

Critical dependencies

The most important critical dependency pertains to the next steps in scaling up the project to a broader segment of markets. In the following steps, the operations of the use case will scale up, in which device manufacturing will need further funding and support, including the identification of funding sources.

Impacts

The impacts related to the recovery of unsold food products and therefore to the reduction of food waste in SoGeMi wholesale markets are covered in detail in the deliverables D7.5, D1.5, and D3.3. In those, the business models, the social return on investments, and the environmental impacts are respectively described. In order to calculate the environmental impacts of this specific use case, a quantitative scaling factor was determined. The factor is aligned with the pilot's goal to deploy the food waste recovery protocol beyond SoGeMi and align waste management protocols across Milan's covered markets to better recover food waste.

5.3.2. Food Market 4.0

Introduction of the use case

The second use case is Food Market 4.0. The goal is to deploy a food tracing dashboard in Milan, starting with local producers via SoGeMi, and extending to specific covered markets (i.e., Farm to Fork). Specifically, the Food Market 4.0 solutions is an integrated system of both hardware and software solutions for Milan's covered municipal markets which aims to improve traceability and prevent food waste. Food Market 4.0 Dashboard includes inventory tracking, logistics planning, and controlling for the inbound and outbound of fruit and vegetables flowing through the municipal markets. The solution supports the matching of supply and demand for food goods, and can be implemented for both new B2B and B2C procurement models. The tracking component of this solution also has the possibility of being connected to the Foody Zero Waste solution which allows for the further reduction of food waste. Additionally, Food Market 4.0 also provides physical touchpoints such as a smart scale (Figure 27), reusable crates with integrated RFID (Figure 28), and a UHF RFID reader with related antennas to enlarge its signal. The Food Market 4.0 prototypical solutions have been tested during January 2022 within the Morsenchio Municipal Covered Market, in collaboration with a fruit and vegetable market vendor and the boxes provider (CPR⁴³ system).

⁴³ <https://www.cprsystem.it/en/>

Figure 29: Smart scale system with RFID reader

Figure 30: Reusable and foldable crates with RFID tag

Description of the 5 years goal

The five year goal for Food Market 4.0 is to deploy a system of food traceability dashboard in Milan - from local producers through SoGeMi wholesalers to specific covered markets, including the Food Market 4.0 dashboard and connected hardware (smart scale, RFID crate, RFID readers).

What are the barriers to this goal?

In the problem analysis definition, the Milan pilot was able to further elaborate which are the different barriers and challenges to be solved to achieve the five year goal.

The first core **behavioural and incentive barrier** identified is the need to convince market distributors of the validity of and necessity for tracking, but also to stimulate a bottom-up approach beginning with covered market operators (i.e., food stalls) to explain clearly the value proposition of the digital tracking system. Connected to the market operators, the varying level of digital literacy of the users was a key **technological** barrier rapidly identified - to ensure the uptaking of these digital tools and avoid creating gaps in the supply chain, should an operator not be able to use digital tools, an important upskilling work must be undertaken.

Technological and **financial** barriers were also identified during the visioning of the scaling phase of the dashboard and its hardware components to other covered markets. Indeed, the high cost of digitisation and sensorisation of the covered markets raises the question of who to distribute costs throughout the deployment of the digital tracking system. Additionally, the manufacturing capabilities to produce the hardware and software capabilities to upgrade and maintain the software are technological challenges that must be solved to ensure the medium term sustainability of the dashboard. Directly linked to this challenge is the need to develop the business model surrounding the tracking service to **finance** this digital infrastructure (and hardware production/procurement). The development of the business model is therefore a **financial and business** challenge that must be solved to achieve the 5-year goal.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

The identified barriers and challenges raised by the local actors led to the elaboration of a detailed timeline to scale the pilot's solution after REFLOW and reach the defined goal. The table below compiles, to begin, the key steps achieved within the REFLOW project by the Milan pilot, followed by all the necessary actions within the use case Food Market 4.0 to reach the desired goal in a five year period, the latter having been developed within the Backcasting exercise. Overall, along the Backcasting timeline, 15 necessary actions were identified to ensure the achievement of the 5-year goal of Food Market 4.0 of deploying a food traceability dashboard in Milan - from local producers to SoGeMi to specific covered markets (Farm to Fork).

During Reflow project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework lever	Associated WPs
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1. Identify five municipal covered markets and big players in food and waste streams.	Baseline assessment	WP1
2. Identify tracking solutions to apply in covered markets through co-creation and co-design workshops.	Data and tech	WP2 and WP5
3. Evaluate the feasibility of ideas previously elaborated through co-design workshops.	Engaging and Convening	WP1, WP4
4. Validation of ideas through a series of experiments and prototypes (use cases) involving customers and citizens.	Prototyping and experiments	WP2
5. Complete a real-world test of the prototype of a tracking dashboard in Morsenchio market.	Prototyping and experiments	WP2 and WP5

Post Reflow Project

From year 1 to year 3:

- 6. Pilot with a small group of dedicated operators in SoGeMi that sell their products to Morsenchio market
- 7. Stabilise tracking around specific food flows from SoGeMi to pilot market and add the flows from producers to market, to final consumers (Farm to Fork)
- 8. Show the outcomes of the pilot to all actors in SoGeMi to convince them of using the dashboard

From year 3 to year 5:

- 9. Compare REFLOW outputs to currently tracking systems and models
- 10. Assess the cost of ownership of the system and dashboard, create an ownership structure and build on initial business model
- 11. Create a standardised system to include SoGeMi's current tracking infrastructure used by its seafood market, and add the meat and flower markets to the system.
- 12. Give to SoGeMi distributors digital training to accelerate uptake of digital tools

13. Organise awareness and educational sessions with covered markets across Milan
14. Replicate the dashboard model to other SoGeMi markets and covered markets in Milan
15. Connect the covered markets and SoGeMi markets through the dashboard

Critical Actions

In order to substantiate the transformative potential of the selected 5-year goal, 5 critical actions were highlighted by the pilot team, 3 of which were further expanded upon with the pilot team to define the key sub-actions and identified all the relevant stakeholders.

Figure 31: Critical actions co-identified for Food Market 4.0 with the Milan pilot to achieve the 5-year goal

Piloting the tracking dashboard

The piloting phase is the first critical action highlighted. It pertains to the piloting of the Food Market 4.0 devices with participating fruits and vegetables wholesalers in SoGeMi, and the market operators in Morsenchio market to assess how the dashboard and the different hardware components (smart scale, RFID crates) perform in optimising logistics, increasing transparency, and reducing waste. This requires first to gather initial financing to fund the piloting phase (*economic and financial incentives* lever). The dashboard can be used in Morsenchio Market but will require in parallel the training of market distributors and operators to increase their digital literacy skills (*capacity building* lever) and facilitate the use of the dashboard. Iteratively, the dashboard will

be refined and simplified based on their user feedback to increase overall ergonomics and user-friendliness. Throughout this action, a key sub-action will revolve around the maintenance and updating of the dashboard as its design evolves, requiring technical partners, such as Polimi (*data and technology* lever). Finally, the dashboard will need to be connected with REFLOW OS. The principal stakeholders required were participating SoGeMi wholesalers, Morsenchio market distributor and operators, CPR (crate providers), Polimi, and REFLOW OS developers, which all were involved in the testing phase.

Strengthen business model and ownership structure

This action is devoted to the strengthening of Food Market 4.0 ownership structure and business model. It will build upon the business model development work instigated in T7.6 and described in REFLOW Deliverable 7.5. First, the potential incentives structures that could support the dashboard development and uptake in Milan covered markets must be evaluated for both feasibility and how easily they could be integrated into ownership models that enable the long-term financial sustainability of Food Market 4.0. Ownership models must be further explored with relevant stakeholders - from the Municipality of Milan, to SoGeMi, to the covered markets, and logistic partners, such as CPR (*experimenting and prototyping*). Through the iterative development of the ownership structure and business model(s), the overall goal will be to achieve the buy-in from all local producers/distributors into the digital tracking system to reach a full coverage of the local food flows from SoGeMi local producers to the 'champion' markets (e.g., Morsenchio, Rombon) (*innovative partnership* lever).

Deploy dashboard to other SoGeMi wholesalers and covered markets

This action revolves around the deployment of the Food Market 4.0 dashboard to the majority of SoGeMi wholesalers and to a selection of municipal covered markets. First, to incentivize the use of the dashboard, the Municipality can support the inclusion of data collection and monitoring requirements in its tenders' application for the management of covered markets during the renewal of their management contracts (*legislation/regulation* lever). Additionally, as a step further, the Municipality can include best practices in terms of digitization of data collection and monitoring in future tenders. Jointly, with the top-down approach of public tenders, the bottom-up upskilling of digital skills for market operators will be a requirement to ensure that no market operator or wholesaler is left behind during the digitization of Milan's food system (*capacity building* lever). External funding will need to be sought to support the scaling of the dashboard, as well as to cover the digital training costs, be it in the form of public-private investment, public funding, or private investors, depending on the business and ownership models previously agreed upon (*financial measures* and *economic and financial incentives* levers). To facilitate the incentive-based approach of the deployment of the dashboard, governance structures surrounding the payments or re-distribution of benefits stemming from a reduction in waste management costs will need to be developed - and integrated into future tenders. Finally, partnerships will need to be clearly formalised between the SoGeMi, the covered markets, and the different logistical private actors, such as CPR systems to enable the dashboard to be fully integrated in each organisation's processes.

Critical dependencies

As a critical dependency underlined by the REFLOW Milan Pilot, the capacity and competency of local market managers in relation to the digitalisation of the market itself needs dedicated resources and funding. These are as yet unidentified, while essential. The identification of diversified funding sources to pilot

the dashboard, such as under the Food Policy Budget, Italian Recovery Plan, and other EU funds should be undertaken. The identification of other EU funding/resources (EU sources) to build the capacity, the competencies and the dedicated resources is also deserving of attention, and overcome 'first mover' investment.

Secondly, a partnership is required between the economic operators, SoGeMi and CPR in order to move forward with the structural and logistical connection with vendors. This will require identification of other services providers comparable to CPR, stimulating work with a range of service providers, and in addition, making data public to assure future replicability and impact of the project.

A third dependency is that SoGeMi is a semi-private enterprise required to conform to public tender guidelines for digitalisation in their associated markets. SoGeMi is required to act as a critical partner in the development of such tender guidelines.

Finally, future agreements will be required between stakeholders involved in the digitalisation of the food value chain in order to ensure uniformity and compatibility. In this regard, stakeholder co-creation of guidelines is key, as well as defining clearly the incentives and benefits accruing to parties from participation.

Impact

The impacts related to the tracking of food flows across Milan's markets are covered in detail in the deliverables D7.5 and D1.5. In those, the business models and the social return on investments are respectively described.

6. PARIS PILOT

6.1 Pilot Introduction

The REFLOW Paris Pilot focuses on city-wide timber and wood use in the temporary construction industry, including events. The Pilot sets out to quantify and qualify the waste material flows generated from such temporary use, through the development of new models and digital tools. These tools are aimed at facilitating the reuse of wood materials and products in order to contribute to the acceleration of circular models in this sector.

The Pilot prototypes and tests digital tracking and scanning tools leveraging computational design techniques in their incubator, Driven x REFLOW⁴⁴. By identifying and quantifying these material flows, wood can be monitored and reintegrated into manufacturing processes, extending the material lifecycle. Besides this track-and-trace function, these tools are capable of generating databases of wood products. The goal of this inventorisation is to support the development of an agile digital marketplace that will increase material exchange between the events industry and the temporary construction sector.

6.2 Ecosystem mapping

The Circular Loops Diagram depicts what circularity loops the pilots are working on in relation to specific use cases developed through REFLOW activities. The Pilot effort has been highlighted in the Circular Loops Diagram through the identification of loops and impacts for two main use cases:

1. Dimensionneuse
2. RE-Label.

For each use case, several closed loops are highlighted for recycling, refurbishing, manufacturing and maintaining the material resource, as well as for regenerating them. With each loop identifying the relevant stakeholders and current or future connections which are required to enable the function corresponding to the loop.

⁴⁴ <https://drivenbyvolumes.io/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

Figure 32: Paris Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3.

Regarding the activities under the Maison et Objet use case, the following existing or future loops have been identified:

Recycle	Between <i>collection</i> and <i>part manufacturer</i> by recycling timber wood and wood elements.
Reuse	Between <i>collection</i> and <i>service provider/retailer</i> by reusing wood after a process of transformation.
Maintain/Prolong/Share	Between <i>collection</i> and <i>service provider/retailer</i> by reusing wood without previous transformation process.
Refurbish/Remanufacture	Between <i>collection</i> and <i>product manufacturer</i> by refurbishing and

remanufacturing wood that cannot be used as is.

Regarding the Re-Label use case and its identified loops, the following impacts have been identified:

Recycle	Between <i>product manufacturer-</i> and <i>parts manufacturer</i> (wood industry) by recycling damaged panels of wood and wood scraps into reusable wood.
Maintain/Prolong/Share	Between <i>collection</i> and <i>service provider</i> by facilitating the return of toys from the collection point and therefore prolong their life cycle.

6.3 Selected use cases

6.3.1 DIMENSIONNEUSE

Introduction of the use case

The material flow analysis performed on wood for the region of Ile-de-France, in the scope of the Deliverable D3.2, has shown that a large fraction of the wood waste collected ends up in landfill or is downcycled for low-value material or energy recovery. used. In total, about 920,000 tons of wood enter the Ile-de France waste system annually, with 24,000 tons coming from the event and cultural sector. A large fraction of this waste, including MDF and plywood, has the potential to be reused, and this is especially applicable in the case of temporary events.

The first use case, the Dimensionneuse, is a semi-automated scanner for different materials (timber/ wood in Paris) through which a network of users is created. The collected data (through the scanning device) is visible in an online database which facilitates the further use (REFLOW OS). The scanner creates digital inventory but does not manage it. Therefore, it must be connected to another system (inventory management system or another reuse marketplace). The customer can scan their wood (which they do not have further use for) and the database shows and provides it to potential next users. The goal is to create new standards and make it easier for existing databases to get more material-specific. The scanning device can be sold to existing databases/ marketplaces to increase their efficiency. In the future the scanning device can be used for other materials to enable the reuse of the respective material. A smartphone app and website will be integrated to Dimensionneuse to enable craftspeople access to the database of materials and to facilitate the exchange through a connection to external marketplaces.

Within the timeline of the REFLOW project, the pilot was able to implement the Dimensionneuse system (Figure 32) during the September 2021 Maison & Objet⁴⁵ event. The wood collected from the exhibitors, totalising 3.5 tons, was all scanned through the Dimensionneuse, which provides a material database for the design of modular furniture (Figure 33). The new furniture was designed by WAO⁴⁶, an architecture firm, to first serve as exhibition

⁴⁵ <https://www.maison-objet.com/en/paris>

⁴⁶ <https://wao.paris/>

stands in the March 2022 *Maison & Objet* edition (postponed due to Covid from January 2022), and to then be transformed as office furniture at the new Fab City Paris location. Within this use case, the Paris pilot team covers a role as a Paris SAS⁴⁷ which operates by providing consulting activities, facilitating reuse, and as well as connecting actors in the network of REFLOW.

Figure 33: Dimensionneuse system used during the use case

⁴⁷ SAS refers to *société par actions simplifiée* which is a type of business entity in France.

Figure 34: Dimensionneuse database

Description of the 5-years goal

As a 5-years goal, the Paris Pilot proposes to deploy the Dimensionneuse protocol and system developed at Maison & Objet at five major events of comparable size and intention. Part of this goal is to also develop partnerships with waste collectors for the events for improving sorting and collection, in which the waste produced is reduced and better valorised, with a clear reference to the creation of new products, as well as reuse and repurposing of existing elements. The ultimate purpose of the goal is to be able to collect and reuse wood waste to be reused as scenography or furniture in either future edition of the events, or in diverse context.

What are the barriers to this goal?

The Paris pilot has highlighted that events and temporary architecture use a massive amount of wood material. As the pilot was aware that there are an array of barriers to deploy successfully the protocol, the team worked on identifying those barriers.

The first major barriers to deploy the protocol in large scale events are **behavioural and logistical**, as the event sector has long established practices, with a mature logistical environment. For a seamless integration of the

solution, the entire processes (e.g. workflow, space requirement, financial, and human resources) must be rethought.

An additional significant barrier revolves around **regulatory challenges**. Current waste management framework does not require the **categorization of wooden waste** in ways which are optimal to this kind of circular practice. This negatively affects the **accurate forecasting** of material which will be designated as 'waste' by the event organisers, in order to convey the information to the user/buyer, for planning purposes. A regulatory framework governing such practices by organisers is fundamental in achieving the goal.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

This table compiles a set of necessary actions within the use case Maison & Objet to reach the desired 5-years goal of having five major events following the protocol developed with Maison & Objet and having partnerships with waste collectors developed for the events for better sorting, collection, and valorisation. The table below indicates in chronological order a set of actions required to reach the attainable goal.

During Reflow project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework Levers	Associated WPs/tasks
1. Develop a process for reusing wood in temporary events set-up and raise awareness on the marketplace.	Awareness raising Prototyping and experimenting	WP7
2. Analyse the potential business models for the solution. (T7.6)	Prototyping and experimenting	WP 7
3. Develop a business model for Dimensionneuse. (T7.6)	Prototyping and experimenting	WP7
4. Develop a best practices guide on how to use and reuse materials ("ways to transform" (ongoing)) and share it across the industry.	Capacity building	WP6
5. Perform a database experimentation using Dimension-use data (the storage facility). (T5.3)	Prototyping and experimenting	WP2 and WP5
6. Orient and mentor incubated projects to develop new business models for CE based on digital technologies.	Capacity building	WP7
7. Pilot the wood collection protocol and the Dimensionneuse at the September 2021 edition of Maison et Objet.	Prototyping and experimenting	WP1

7.bis. Pilot building modular designs for exhibitors, from the previously collected wood, at the March 2022 edition of Maison et Objet and to be reused in the new Fab City Paris location.	Prototyping experimenting and	WP1
8 Assess the scalability of the protocol with information on the needs of the events through interviews and surveys.	Baseline Assessment	WP1

Post Reflow project

From year 1 to year 2:

- 9. Implement a tracking system at the event scale that is compatible with the Dimensionneuse.
- 10. Perform a research/ study on the reusability of materials available in the region in the temporary event sector.
- 11. Forecast the circulation of the material from the provider (event organisers are producing "waste") to end customers (buyers that are using the reuse materials).
- 12. Perform a logistical feasibility assessment for scaling up the Dimensionneuse solution to more events.

From year 2 to year 3:

- 13. Finalise the outline for information and logistics (quality, numbers of use, dimension, storage conditions) needed by event organisers on the wooden elements (to incorporate in the Dimensionneuse) based on logistical assessment and forecasting.
- 14. Show the viability of the model to event organisers and exhibitors through adjusted business models and financial assessments.
- 15. Onboard the different actors of the Maison et Objet events or other large events selected (e.g. organisers, exhibitors, waste management team) on the requirements of the common platform to collect data and execute the reuse protocol.

From year 3 to year 5:

- 16. Federate a network of different actors from different fields to facilitate the reuse of materials (e.g. designers, event organisers, local waste handlers, exhibitors).
- 17. Create and enable physical infrastructure in the city and logistical protocol to manage logistics of the wood

elements based on the requirements of the actors previously assessed (e.g. location, available space, cost).

18. Make the availability and specifications (data) of reuse materials visible to different actors in advance (Certification through REFLOW OS, Dimensionneuse).

19. Promote the platform to reuse and repurpose furniture/ constructions.

20. Align the Dimensionneuse protocol with the AGEC⁴⁸ law.

21. Create a mandate for the event organisers and exhibitors to share information on what materials are being used in the event.

22. Implement a tracking system and material passport across different events.

Critical Actions

Some actions have been identified as critical (highlighted above) and have been detailed with levers and the stakeholder ecosystem required for the action.

⁴⁸ France adopted the Anti-waste Law in 2020. The law aims to eliminate waste and pollution from the design stage and transform the system of production, distribution, and consumption from a linear to a circular economic model (source <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/frances-anti-waste-and-circular-economy-law>).

Figure 35: Critical actions co-identified for Dimensionneuse with the Paris pilot to achieve the 5-year goal

In the array of actions listed above, the six critical actions identified will happen after the conclusion of the three years of REFLOW. These have been further discussed with the pilot as they will be key in the achievement of the 5-years goal.

Tracking system

In order to deploy the wood reuse protocol consistently across events, a material tracking system compatible with the Dimensionneuse must be implemented at the event scale in Paris. The implementation of a tracking system will allow the data collection of available materials and will facilitate the inventory management and exchanges. The tracking system will require the alignment of various actors along the

supply chain, such as event organisers (i.e. Maison et Objet organisers), waste sorters (i.e. Millenium⁴⁹ and Valdelia⁵⁰), wood manufacturers, resource centres, or co-working spaces (e.g. Fab City Paris⁵¹). To get the most actors involved, it will be critical to raise awareness about the benefits of reusing wood products and circular construction. After, it will be key to develop logistics around data collection and making materials easily available. This tracking system will require both an iterative approach of trials and errors (*prototyping and experimentation* lever) to develop the required hardware and software (*data and tech* lever) with the support of engaged stakeholders in the event ecosystems (*engaging and convening*) that will need to be trained appropriately to use these new tracking protocols (*capacity building* lever).

Circular material forecast

This critical action consists of forecasting the potential circular materials available within the sector and events (i.e. Maison et Objet), and the opportunities for reuse. This critical action first looks at the requirements for reusing materials and at the regulation on waste in events settings such as Maison et Objet (*legislation and regulations* lever). The following key sub-action should be to identify locations and large events organisers (e.g. FAIRSPACE, SAFI) in the city to collaborate with and to coordinate material and waste managers of multiple events (e.g. Maison et Objet, FIAC⁵²) (*baseline assessment and innovative partnerships* levers). Another key sub-action would be to develop a successful test case to showcase the benefits of reusing wood (e.g. financial gains) to key actors (e.g. Maison et Objet's exhibitors, Millenium and Valdelia) (*engaging and convening, awareness raising, and capacity building* levers).

Scaling assessment

This critical action consists of performing a logistical feasibility assessment for scaling up the Dimensionneuse solution to more events. After the success of the prototype at the scale of one event (i.e. 2021 and 2022 editions of Maison et Objet), some parameters must be assessed to evaluate the replicability potential to other events. More efforts will have to be targeted towards assessing the logistical needs, especially regarding the availability of physical spaces for storage purposes (*baseline assessment* lever). Reusing materials will require significant temporary storage space that will need to be quantified through the means of surveys answered by event organisers (*engaging and convening* lever). Based on the location of most targeted actors, storage capacity will need to be found in Paris, which presents a challenge in itself. The Municipality of Paris could potentially be a key stakeholder to help in providing adequate space. An organisation will also need to be identified to manage the storage and develop a common storage management guide (*capacity building* lever). Based on all those requirements, a cost feasibility study will be conducted in partnerships with financial institutions (e.g. BPI France) (*fiscal measures* lever). The scaling up evaluation will be primarily built upon the assessment of current operations.

⁴⁹ <https://www.millenium-sas.com/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.valdelia.org/>

⁵¹ <http://fabcity.paris/en/home/>

⁵² <https://www.fiac.com/>

Collect information

After assessing the needs of the various actors involved in the Maison et Objet events or in other large events selected, the following critical action consists of onboarding the actors on the data collection process and the use of the Dimensionneuse platform to reuse materials (*engaging and convening* lever).

The onboarding of a wide range of cultural sector actors will allow the widening of the database and the diversity of materials available. Workshops will be organised with the cultural sector to present the key principles of the circular economy and get multiple organisations on board (*communication and capacity building* levers). The organisation previously identified as a storage manager and coordinator could partner with Fab City Paris to share a common guide on the best practices to follow..

Create visibility of data

This action relies on engaging and convening relevant actors and communicating about the interface and service offered by the Dimensionneuse. Financial mechanisms and a narrative should be developed to increase the visibility of the reused materials platform (*fiscal measures and communication* levers).

Again, this will require a multi-stakeholder coordination to improve the interface and make it attractive which could be powered by Fab City Paris or Ars Longa⁵³ (*innovative partnerships and data and tech* lever). In addition to the sector's stakeholders, developers and web designers should be involved and identified, as well as communication actors.

Create mandate for organisers

In the Backcasting timeline, one of the last actions before achieving the 5-years goal is the alignment between the protocol and current waste and procurement regulations, (*legislation and regulations* lever).

Aligning protocols with the AGEC (law against wastage and for circular economy) law, which was instituted in 2020, would be crucial. Meanwhile, a mandate for the event exhibitors and organisers should also be created by a regulating body (municipal/ national government) to share information on the materials used. The enforcement to disclose information about the wood flows would increase transparency between all wood users and offer more opportunities for material exchange. Capacity building across all event organisers to ensure adequate sorting would be crucial (*capacity building* lever). The organisation Halte à l'Obsolescence Programmé (HOP)⁵⁴, working to fight programmed obsolescence, has been working to implement the AGEC law, and therefore could be an experienced partner to develop new regulations with organisations such as the Union Française des Métiers de l'Environnement (UNIMEV)⁵⁵ and Fab City Paris.

⁵³ <http://www.arslonga.fr/en/home/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.halteobsolescence.org/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.unimev.fr/>

Critical dependencies

Although it has been underlined by the pilot that the use case does not present significant critical risk in the further realisation of the project, the alignment with AGECE law represents an important future action to be tackled. The establishment of future connections with fair spaces will be instrumental to outreach the broader goal.

Moreover, working with the events sector during the uncertain period of the Covid-19 pandemic situation has created a critical risk external to the project.

Impacts

The impacts related to reusing wood from the event sector are covered in detail in the deliverables D7.5, D1.5, and D3.3. In those, the business models, the social return on investments, and the environmental impacts are respectively described. In order to calculate the environmental impacts of this specific use case, a quantitative scaling factor was determined. The factor is aligned with the pilot's goal to reuse more wood from events and align waste management protocols to better valorise wood waste.

6.3.2 RE-LABEL

Introduction of the use case

From the material flow analysis of wood products in Paris, it was shown that the commercial sector accounts for the largest producer of wood waste with about a third of the total volumes of the region⁵⁶. In order to raise awareness about wooden consumer goods, their fabrication process, and the "value" of the wood, while minimising wood waste, the second identified use case, the **RE-Label** initiative, was created. It offers a toolbox including a platform and services to local makers in order to better valorise their sustainable products and reduce the generation of wood scraps. The improved valorisation is envisioned and enacted by providing a certificate for the product, which shows the specificities and singularities of their creation. The body of information includes origin, measurements, history, and quality of the material, and is gathered in the RE-Label certificate edited by an online generator. Thus, the document is dated and signed by the designer or the workshop manager. The RE-Label works on coordinating the community and improving collaboration around exchanges of ideas and best practices

Through the REFLOW process, the RE-Label has been launched with a selection of small workshops mostly located in Paris, and with a few in Nancy (Figure 35). Several projects ranging from furniture for local retailers to

⁵⁶ REFLOW Deliverable 3.2. Urban Metabolism Analysis: Initial Assessment, 2021

micro-architecture and toys, have been labelled with the RE-Label and made visible on the organisation's website⁵⁷. The website allows other organisations to label their product by filling the survey available online.

Figure 36: RE-Label certificate

Description of the 5-years goal

The 5-years goal aims at increasing the awareness and motivation for customers to buy RE-Label products, to make people aware of the value of wood and its waste and the efforts put in fabrication. In a timeframe of five years, the goal is to have this protocol present in ten to twenty local maker communities across France.

What are the barriers to this goal?

The Paris pilot has identified several interconnected barriers spanning logistical, behavioural, technological, and regulatory aspects. **Logistically**, the inventorisation of available wood waste and stock for a large number of workshops is linked to the different workflows of each workshop which can be hard to map and predict. The implementation of a user-friendly software to predict waste flows consists of a **technological** challenge to be solved, and development **costs and time** implications can make it even more difficult.

At the **behavioural** level, artisanal products that have a higher cost than mass-produced industrial products may not be attractive to the general public. People are not necessarily inclined to buy locally produced and sustainable products, and incentives or educational measures are needed to promote the shift in individual behaviours. From a **regulatory** perspective, there is a lack of regulation around product manufacturing processes allowing for the production of low-quality and unsustainable products and for the large production of wood waste. A set of regulations for workshops with the AGECE law would support the implementation of the RE-Label on a larger scale.

⁵⁷ <https://re-label.eu/>

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

This table compiles all the necessary actions within the use case RE-Label to reach the desired five years goal of increasing the awareness and motivation for customers to buy RE-Label products and to make people aware of the value of wood and its waste.

During Reflow project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework Levers	Associated WPs
1. Perform an inventory of wood workshops and the wood waste in Paris.	Baseline assessment	WP1
2. Develop the RE-Label generators, software and methodology	Prototyping and experimentation	WP2 and WP5
3. Test the RE-Label and the software with local workshops and actors.	Prototyping and experimentation	WP2 and WP5
4. Select ten workshops and design agencies in Paris and a few in Nancy to implement the RE-Label.	Engaging and Convening	WP4
5. The designers create various products from the wood waste of the workshops and sell them.	Prototyping and experimentation	wp7 or N/A
6. Create a guidebook to showcase the methodology of the organisation of the clusters and partnership methods.	Capacity building	WP6

Post Reflow project

From year 1 to year 2:

7. Develop a tool to measure wood stocks and the needs of craftsmen and designers.

From year 2 to year 3:

8. With the tool measuring wood stocks and needs developed, quickly connect workshops with designers and makers.

9. Promote the RE-Label through events and tenders.

10. Develop more workshops across France using the RE-Label after adopting the Paris use case.

From year 3 to year 5:

11. Identify coordinators for each cluster/community (cluster of actors rather than a geographical location) for a horizontal collaboration.

12. Build a community of actors who work with the label to set up a national proposition.

13. Partner up with ADEME (Agence de la transition écologique)⁵⁸ and AFNOR⁵⁹ (Association française de normalisation).

14. Establish an online marketplace to sell RE-Label products.

Critical Actions

Some actions have been identified as critical (highlighted above) and have been detailed with levers and the stakeholder ecosystem required for the action.

⁵⁸ <https://www.ademe.fr/the-website-is-changing>

⁵⁹ <https://normalisation.afnor.org/>

Figure 37: Critical actions co-identified for Re-Label with the Paris pilot to achieve the 5-year goal

Promotion

The second use case proposed by the Paris pilot is intent on raising awareness about reusing wood scraps. Following the infographic (Figure 36), the ninth action looks into the **promotion of the RE-Label project** through training, events, and tenders (*awareness raising* and *communication* lever). The pilot plans on developing professional training for designers in partnership with local actors such as Vilette Makerz, Les Canaux, or Paris Fabrik, which will build capacity in the field. The pilot has also planned on applying in tenders with consulting firms, as they already did with UTOPIES.

Scale up

The tenth critical action corresponds to the **scaling up of the RE-Label process**, where more workshops across France start using the RE-Label after adopting the REFLOW methodology and mirroring the Paris use case. To adequately scale up the solution, a large network of actors in the field must be connected between one another and to Fab City Paris and Ars Longa (*innovative partnership* lever). Starting from a craft scale, the pilot wants to think of growing on the consumer market, which will require the buy-in from a large number of

consumers, interior architects, and designers. The participation at events was identified as an important step to grow the existing network (*engaging and convening and capacity building levers*). Between workshops and wood collectors, a close collaboration should be developed, facilitated by the implementation of technological tools (e.g. REFLOW OS) to support the exchange of materials (*data and tech and innovative partnerships levers*).

Partner with the ADEME and ANFOR

To proceed on the action timeline, the following action consists of creating a partnership with **ADEME and ANFOR**. This partnership with important actors in the national ecological transition could facilitate the streamlining of regulations (e.g. AGECE law) and the promotion and implementation of the process (*legislation and regulations lever*). This step should be building upon the previous critical action and the network created.

Establishment of online and physical markets

The last action put forward before reaching the 5-years goal is the creation of a marketplace to sell RE-Label products. RE-Label products are currently sold in the workshops themselves and have been temporarily available in a pop-up shop in Fab City Paris. To increase the visibility and awareness of RE-Label products, it would be necessary to make the products available online (*awareness raising lever*). A basic evaluation of current platforms (e.g. Etsy, WOMA, Dayrize) should be done and the most optimal one for the target audience should be selected (*baseline assessment lever*). To integrate any platform, a financing mechanism and business model should be developed for the RE-Label process (*fiscal measures lever*). However, some challenges were discussed here regarding the proximity of the products to the end consumers. Since the goal of the label is to increase the sustainability of the products, it would not make sense to ship the products over a long distance. This point therefore led to the possibility of making product design files available online (e.g. Wiki Factory), where they could be recreated by other designers. This option is not optimal, however, as it would be extremely difficult to guarantee the compliance of the protocol followed.

Impacts

The impacts (financial and social) related to reusing wood from the event sector are covered in detail in the deliverables D7.5 and D1.5. In those, business models and the social return on investments are respectively described.

7. VEJLE PILOT

7.1 Pilot Introduction

The REFLOW Vejle pilot focuses on plastic waste by gaining insights into urban plastic consumption and increasing the circularity of the city's plastic value chains. The accumulation of non-recyclable plastic, plastic-based waste, and its poor management is a problem faced by Vejle. Working closely with diverse test sites, covering retailers, manufacturers, healthcare facilities and innovation centres, the Vejle pilot has gained valuable insights into the bottlenecks of plastic use, and recycling behaviour in the city.

The pilot project in Vejle dives into three micro-scale test sites in the Western neighbourhood of the city – Vestbyen, where the pilot project runs targeted experimentations, workshops, and engagement sessions to identify and showcase solutions for increased plastic reuse, recovery, and reduction. These test sites include three other initiatives. First, a retail store in the supermarket chain REMA1000⁶⁰ where the pilot focuses on creating circular streams of specific plastic types by prototyping new circular loops for specific plastic containers and scaling this to the rest of REMA 1000 stores in Denmark as well as to other retailers in Denmark and the Nordics. Second, the public housing block Den Gamle Gaard⁶¹, where the pilot focus is to create better and more intuitive sorting systems and information in apartment buildings by engaging citizens and building a local community. The final aim is to develop new sorting prototypes and consequently enable scaling up and replication in other cities. Third, the public elderly home Sofiegården⁶² where the pilot focus is to change the plastic stream in the healthcare sector by prototyping new solutions that will decrease the use of plastic. The aim is to scale up these solutions to the regional/national levels and provide indications for other cities.

The Vejle pilot places a significant emphasis on its citizens as changemakers towards reaching the Vejle pilot's long-term goal of circular plastics. This citizen focus is evident in the solutions that have been developed by the Vejle pilot, which seek to activate a citizen movement by empowering them to become informed and active in the change-making.

The pilot's short-term objectives are:

- to generate better sorting at our test-sites and amongst the citizens in Vejle. This involves an increased knowledge of how to sort plastic waste and awareness about plastic alternatives. We also strive to unlock possibilities to improve reducing, reusing and recycling of plastics in a local context.

The long-term objectives are:

⁶⁰ <https://rema1000.dk/>

⁶¹ <http://www.dengamlegaard-stubberup.dk/>

⁶² <https://sofiegaarden.vejle.dk/>

- to change the plastic streams and create circular streams of specific plastic types. This involves activating a citizen movement with an empowered local community of active and informed citizens, and new solutions to foster methods and tools to reuse plastic and replace plastic in products.

The Circular Loops Diagram strongly reflects the pilot solutions by focusing the attention on two specific ones: Plastic packaging from food packaging in retail and plastic from the healthcare sector.

7.2 Ecosystem mapping

Throughout the REFLOW project, numerous activities have been carried out by the pilot to engage and support the transformation in the Vejle region, which have been reflected and analysed in T5.3 using the Circular Loops Diagram.

The primary Circular Loops Diagram was focused on mapping the entire ecosystem of activities around plastic packaging. The first version of the mapping identified the current linear plastic flows, including the general steps and players in the plastic producing process. This Circular Loops Diagram provides an overview of plastic packaging production, from processing raw materials (fossil fuels) to how it's placed back into waste.

Figure 38: Vejle’s Circular Loops Diagram produced during T5.3.

In the second version of the Circular Loops Diagram, the solutions developed by the Pilot have been highlighted through the identification of loops and impacts for two main use cases:

1. Plastics in food packaging
2. Plastics in healthcare products

The Circular Loops Diagram depicts what circularity loops the pilots are working on in relation to specific use cases developed through REFLOW activities. Highlighting several closed loops for recycling, reusing and regeneration for present and future purposes. Each loop identifies the relevant stakeholders and current or future connections which are required to enable the function corresponding to the loop.

Regarding the healthcare packaging, the following loops have been identified:

Recycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between <i>discarded material</i> and <i>raw material</i> recycling, soft PVC , soft and hard plastics products. - Between <i>discarded material</i> and <i>raw material</i> recycling, currently incinerated packaging of health products.
Reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between <i>consumer</i> (public health institutions) and <i>service provider/retailer</i> (special healthcare product provider) by the reusing of secondary transport packaging.

Regarding the food packaging, the following loops have been identified:

Recycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between <i>discarded material</i> and <i>parts manufactured</i> by recycling currently incinerated food packaging. - Between <i>food retailers</i> and <i>parts manufacturers</i> by recycling candy boxes to candy boxes.
Reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between consumers and food retailers by reusing a refillable container system between citizens and the supermarkets. - Between <i>consumers</i> (public canteen) and <i>product manufacturers</i> (producers of plastic food packaging) by reusing secondary packaging with food suppliers. - Within service provider/retailer between food retailer and food producing industry by recycling flower crates. - Within service provider/retailer between wholesaler and food producing industry - B2B transport packaging.
Regenerate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Between <i>discarded material</i> and <i>raw material</i> by the regeneration of compostable food packaging (compostable meat and cheese trays).

Within these two distinctive focus areas of plastic streams deriving from the food and healthcare industry, the pilot of Vejle decided to focus on two coherent use cases: REMA 1000 and Sofiegården.

7.3 Selected Use Cases

7.3.1 REMA 1000

Introduction of the use case

The first use case of Vejle pilot's consists of reducing plastic waste at a REMA 1000 supermarket. The analysis of the waste stream at REMA 1000 in Vejle, performed within D3.3, highlighted that a total of 13.5% of the mixed waste is composed of plastic waste that has the potential to be recycled. Most of the plastic still found in the waste mainly consisted of candy tubs, unsold packaged food and plastic bags.

The use case and the proposed solutions are developed in a co-creation process with the REMA 1000 management, a local REMA 1000 store in Vejle, the public waste management in Vejle and private operators. The

main purpose is to optimise the sorting possibilities in the local stores and thereby increase the plastic recycling rate; however, the solution also assembles future actions to be taken into account to develop the use case further. These actions include different processes for implementing the new legislation in Denmark, which stipulates waste sorting into ten fractions. The use case implies a scaling up in the longer term to all REMA 1000 stores in Denmark, with approximately 350 stores, and later on will be scaled to the entire Reitan Group in Northern Europe counting around 1,900 stores. The target for this use case through the REFLOW project was set to reduce 0.9 tons of waste sent to the incinerator per store, corresponding to a total of 315 tons per year.

In fact, within the REFLOW timeline, the pilot was able to divert 50% of the plastic waste previously sent for incineration, which amounts to about 33 kg of plastic recovered per week. From this plastic recovered, the major fraction is composed of hard plastic flower trays, flower buckets, and candy buckets, while the remaining plastic waste is mostly composed of unrecyclable plastic bags.

Description of the 5 years goal

As an achievable 5 year goal, the Vejle pilot proposes that all seven Vejle's REMA 1000 stores will follow the REFLOW protocol increasing sorting.

What are the barriers to this goal?

Barriers are often related to a set of problems that are inherently embedded in the pilot. Like the other five pilots, Vejle also has logistic, behavioural, regulatory, and financial barriers to overcome. Within the Plastic Packaging use case, the **logistic** obstacles are related to hygiene requirements such as sterilisation/washing of candy boxes which currently causes warping. Moreover, CO₂/Environmental cost comparisons are needed between alternate packaging options, along with no current criteria are set for the selection of end-of-life waste management for REMA. Another logistical barrier lies in the location of candy factories causing a longer reuse cycle with empty boxes being sent back for washing to the factories.

The main **behavioural** barrier is the need to ensure the recycled alternative supports the environmental goals over the current single-use option. A nuanced understanding of the pros and cons of how best to develop the supply chain and the material selection criteria are critical dimensions to be developed

The current **regulatory** framework is a crucial barrier for plastic (PP) use and reuses in the food sector with strong classifications for food-grade plastics. Elements such as plastic inner lining on non-plastic packaging material need to fulfil food-grade requirements. On the **financial** front, the costs of food-grade materials replacing the plastic packaging, as well as the price-for-price equivalent requirement are also a current barrier. Tackling consistency in supply and reaching market-comparable pricing for recycled plastic fit for food-grade packaging are essential in reaching this goal. Different stakeholders within the logistical supply chain of recycled plastic and waste management operate through different principles, practices, and quality thresholds, leading to operational complexities for any single entity to establish new practices easily without long-term coordination across the supply chain.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

Based on the listed barriers, this table compiles a set of necessary actions within the use case of reducing plastic packaging in a REMA 1000 store to reach the desired goal within five years.

During Reflow Project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework Levers	Associated WPs
1. Assess plastic streams through qualitative and quantitative methods.	Urban management of assets and material flow	WP3
2. Build partnerships between Vejle’s actors to create circular loops.	Innovative partnership	WP4
3. Identify the main critical product at REMA 1000: candy packaging.	Roadmap, strategies and action plans	WP1
4. Identify the causes of the lack of recycling practices.	Roadmap, strategies and action plans	WP1
5. Create awareness initiatives around improving plastic sorting.	Awareness raising Communication	WP1 and WP5

Post- Reflow:

From year 1 to year 2:

- 6. Create an MFA of REMA 1000 packaging to identify the most impactful packaging combined with an impact assessment.
- 7. Perform LCA assessments of alternative packaging compared to the standard packaging: special focus on material use and primary production impacts.
- 8. Identify alternative food-safe packaging scenarios for most critical packaging uses in REMA 1000's own brand.
- 9. Perform comparative LCAs and cost analysis between different reusable packaging vs. the recyclable/disposable material.

From year 2 to year 3:

- 10. Develop a business case for alternative food packaging at REMA 1000 in Vejle.

11. Select a few materials and loops (recycling/reusing) to pilot in REMA stores.
12. Adjust current REMA 1000 logistics to pilot the solutions (storage space, transportation).
13. Communicate results from scenario analysis to whole REMA 1000 stores, as well as food retailer associations and national regulatory bodies.

From year 3 to year 5:

14. Develop policies on waste management for all REMA stores while collaborating with municipalities- now each store is responsible for their waste handling with a shared protocol.
15. Recommend national policies and guidelines by retailers and municipalities to the National governing bodies.
16. Scaling up and replication of REMA pilot protocols across different food retailers within Denmark .
17. Expansion of physical infrastructure for recycled plastics in the city.

Critical Actions

Along the Backcasting timeline, 17 actions were identified as necessary to the achievement of the 5-year goal for the elimination of plastic food packaging. In order to substantiate the transformative potential of the goal, out of the total list of actions, the Vejle pilot has been identifying which actions can be classified as critical and what levers and stakeholders are needed to perform these actions.

Figure 39: Critical actions co-identified for REMA's 1000 solution with the Vejle pilot to achieve the 5-year goal

Baseline Assessments

The first critical action refers to the analysis of REMA 1000 food packaging and the identification of suitable (economically/technically) alternatives. This action can mainly be described in three steps: identifying the major packaging flows and their impacts, performing research and testing on alternative materials, and exploring the feasibility of implementing the alternative materials and solutions. The levers of implementation connected to this process are the baseline assessment, the social, environmental, and economic evaluation and the deployment of data and technology. Research institutions such as Metabolic⁶³, DTU (Danmarks Tekniske Universitet)⁶⁴, and Materiom⁶⁵ can be key stakeholders to perform those steps.

⁶³<https://www.metabolic.nl/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.dtu.dk/english>

⁶⁵<https://materiom.org/>

Communication of results

The next critical action refers to the communication of results from the scenario analysis, which are communicated to REMA 1000 stores, as well as food retailer associations and national regulatory bodies. Communicating the results should facilitate the adoption of alternatives by other actors. The levers are prototyping and experimental, along with engaging and convening. Those levers are tagged to the key sub-actions taken into account to pull the critical action. These sub-actions are the communication from the pilots about the insights to facilitate the adoption of alternative practices. The stakeholders will be actors within the packaging and recycling industries, Coop Salling Group⁶⁶, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)⁶⁷, and national regulatory entities.

Waste Policy Creation

This critical action regards internal policy creation. It was highlighted that most stores had different waste management protocols, without being coordinated between one another. Hence, internal policies on waste management will be developed for all REMA 1000 stores while collaborating with municipalities. The goal is to have each store following clear guidelines and taking on the responsibilities for sorting and recycling their waste. The key sub-actions to take on forward would be for the Reitan group⁶⁸ to perform assessments of national waste regulations and to work along the regulations in place to properly handle food packaging waste, which pull on the legislation and regulation lever of implementation. Moreover, each local branch should have the responsibility to assess available end-of-life infrastructures in place (local and external), hence doing a proper baseline assessment of the facilities.

National Policy creation

After implementing internal policies, for REMA 1000 stores, the following action to scale up the number of stores adopting the REFLOW protocol pertains to advocating for national policies and guidelines. Those would be recommended by retailers and municipalities to the National governing bodies. The key sub-actions to execute this action are to do an assessment of national waste regulations in Denmark and for retailers to partner with municipalities to drive change forward. The national environmental protection agency should be involved with the organisation De samvirkende Købmænd⁶⁹ and COOP and Salling group to change the regulations.

Critical dependencies

In each of the critical actions listed above to reduce the plastic in the waste stream of supermarkets in Vejle, REMA 1000 is identified as the key stakeholder. The relationship between the pilot and the chain is currently strong and the pilot relies mostly on it to adopt the changes. This creates a high dependency on the long term partnership with REMA 1000 to continue to adopt the protocol. The pilot should start

⁶⁶<https://sallinggroup.com/>

⁶⁷<https://en.mim.dk/>

⁶⁸<https://reitan.no/no>

⁶⁹<https://dsk.dk/>

collaborating with other supermarket chains and stores in the city to minimise the risk and build other long-lasting relationships.

Impact

The impacts (financial, social, and environmental) related to reducing and diverting from incineration plastic products at REMA 1000 stores will be explained in detail in the deliverables D7.5, D1.5, and D3.3. In those, business models, the social return on investments, and the environmental impacts are respectively described. The scalability factor to evaluate the potential environmental impacts of the solution on a 5 year timescale is described by implementing the REFLOW sorting process at all seven REMA 1000.

7.3.2. Plastics in healthcare products: Sofiegården

Introduction of the use case

After performing the analysis of the plastic consumption in Vejle in Deliverable D3.2, it was possible to highlight the lack of sorting and recycling for plastic at multiple locations in the city. In fact, more than 66% of plastic from industries is sent to incineration without priorly being sorted. Public institutions, despite not having the highest stream in the city, have the capabilities to implement circular actions through public procurement and protocols that can then be replicated by other actors.

The second use case selected by the Vejle pilot takes place in the public elderly home Sofiegården. The pilot has implemented a sorting protocol to divert plastic from incineration. The solution enables staff in care facilities, including nursing homes, to sort plastic waste directly on site while performing other tasks. The Mobile Sorting Unit has the potential to significantly increase correct sorting and thereby, reduce the amount of plastic waste that ends up in the general waste which is subsequently being incinerated. The device will be based on a design developed within REFLOW in collaboration with the private product design firm, Creos Design. Besides scaling potentials in healthcare centres, the waste in Vejle also sees potential in scaling this solution to other institutions in the Municipality, such as in schools and day-care centres. A test process has been conducted within the Sofiegården, in particular with diapers. The Municipality of Vejle⁷⁰ has the tools and insights it needs to decrease the amount of plastic in both products and packaging coming into the Municipality. This can be both through tender and contracts.

In this use case, the pilot city chose to combine the inputs on circular procurement received from WP4 with the information and knowledge gathered from the pilot's local stakeholders, leading to the development of 10+ procurement policy recommendations given to the municipality and their procurement department. The Sofiegården is considered as a significant benchmark where the examples collected from the local test site were used to demonstrate the potential of circular procurement policy.

⁷⁰<https://www.vejle.dk>

Throughout the REFLOW project, the test site has shown a significant reduction in the amount of plastic thrown away as mixed waste. Thanks to the Mobile Sorting Station, more than 92% of plastic was diverted to recycling, corresponding to 42 kg of plastic waste saved per week. Meanwhile, the pilot has explored how to minimise the waste of resources, starting with the case of diapers. They looked into current procurement protocols for diapers to reduce the avoidable discarded quantity.

Description of the 5 years goal

Within the above use case chosen by the Vejle pilot, the attainable goal to be achieved in five years focuses on the implementation of circularity focused procurement practices (i.e. policy) for plastic-containing healthcare products in healthcare facilities in Vejle and to implement the Mobile Sorting Station at the 17 other elderly centres in the city. The aim is for all non-avoidable plastic products to be used as efficiently as possible, be easily identified, and be diverted away from incineration. In addition to the above, in a timeframe of ten years, the goal is that hospitals and healthcare facilities in Vejle will phase out procurement of PVC-containing products (i.e. blood bags and tubes).

What are the barriers to this goal?

Changing practices in the healthcare industry come with a few obstacles regarding regulation, logistics and finances. First, the healthcare industry is perhaps one of the most **regulated** industries. Health and safety requirements for products used and protocols are strictly defined. This means that replacement products or practices must provide exactly the same standards and functions as those being replaced. For certain products, suitable alternatives might not be available yet on the market.

In the case of the use of plastic at Sofiegården, procurement is often done at the municipality level rather than at each healthcare facility. Therefore, **regulatory** barriers might be faced to change practices or regulations at the local government level. The main challenges for legislation changes often arise from **financial reasons**. Plastic-free products or easily recyclable products are usually not cost competitive and the municipality might not have the capability to cover any extra costs. To overcome this barrier, regulations at a higher level might be needed.

Another hurdle when wanting to make changes to municipal procurement is the long term contracts created with suppliers. Despite the desire to change procurement practices in the near future, existing contracts can sometimes be in effect until three or five years in the future.

What needs to be done to reach this goal?

This table compiles a list of actions necessary to reach the desired goal within five years. Those actions were elaborated to overcome the barriers previously listed.

During Reflow Project:

Activity	REFLOW Framework Levers	Associated WPs/tasks
1. Identify plastic streams through qualitative and quantitative methods.	Urban management of assets and material flows	WP3
2. Conduct a value chain and stakeholder analysis for the actors involved in healthcare packaging in Vejle.	Urban management of assets and material flows	WP3
3. Create partnerships within the healthcare sector: manufacturers, service providers and consumers.	Innovative partnerships	WP4
4. Visit Sofiegården and conduct interviews to assess the current most used materials in the healthcare facility.	Baseline assessment	WP1
5. Create working group meetings to assess the needs of the facilities and create a roadmap for implementation.	Engaging and convening	WP4
6. Create a prototype workshop where alternative materials would be used.	Prototyping and experimentations	WP3
7. Plan the prototype and road mapping with the stakeholders involved.	Prototyping and experimentations	WP3

Post-Reflow Project:

9. Conduct research on how procurement happens across municipal and regional scales and how it interacts with different Ministries (environment, health).

10. Vejle Municipality convenes municipal and regional procurement departments to assess the opportunities and needs amongst procurement officials.

11. Use Sofiegården as a case study to create an inventory of plastic products purchased via municipal procurement software.

12. Based on Sofiegården inventory of products, create a life cycle screening to identify the most critical products that require replacement.

13. For most critical products, create an alternative assessment to analyse the market readiness of preferable solutions.

14. Create a collaboration between procurement departments in the city for an open innovation challenge to replace products that should be replaced.

15. The Municipality of Vejle, together with regional procurement departments, pilots a scoring system for healthcare products.

16. Select a few alternative products for testing pilots in multiple departments of the health institutions.

17. Procurement software that is used by municipal and regional procurement departments integrates a scoring/ rating system to support health care procurement officials across Denmark to select the best healthcare product options.

18. Integrate circularity into the national green procurement guidelines for the health sector.

Critical Actions

Along the Backcasting timeline, 18 actions were identified as necessary to the achievement of the 5-year goal for the plastic regulation in healthcare. In order to substantiate the transformative potential of the goal, out of the total list of actions, four critical actions have been further expanded with the pilots and the key sub-actions and relevant stakeholders were highlighted.

Figure 40: Critical actions co-identified for Sofiegaarden solution with the Vejle pilot to achieve the 5-year goal

Research on procurement

One of the critical actions is researching how procurement works and interacts on various scales in Vejle.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

Through this action, the Municipality of Vejle convenes municipal and regional procurement departments to assess the opportunities and needs amongst procurement officials. The Danish Design Centre⁷¹ will work closely with the Municipality of Vejle's procurement department to identify the current limitations of changing procurement contracts and the current contracts' timeline (e.g. the contract ending in the near future). Certain tenders will be selected in which the conventional criteria should be turned in circular to change the regulation of the consumption of plastic within healthcare institutions. The possible regional partnerships (e.g. through the union of municipalities (KL⁷²)) will also be investigated to evaluate the possibility of having financial benefits of partnering for procurement. In the case of diapers, a product already identified as critical by the pilot, ESSITY⁷³, a diapers provider can be a key stakeholder to engage with.

Pilot at Sofiegården

The conduction of the pilot at Sofiegården elderly home will be used as a case study to create an inventory of plastic products purchased via the municipal procurement software. Life cycle assessments (LCA) of the most commonly purchased items are conducted to identify the most critical products to be replaced. An inventory of all the products purchased should be made and the products should be sorted based on the purchase frequency. For the most frequently used ones, LCAs will be conducted to identify the most impactful products. Prior to performing LCAs, a research institution (e.g. Metabolic) should be identified and financing should be secured. A baseline assessment is then performed at Sofiegården that will allow the process to be first piloted on a smaller scale.

Innovation challenge for procurement

The pilot identified the following critical action as an innovation challenge to promote innovative alternatives to plastic products in healthcare. This open innovation challenge will take place as a collaboration between procurement, the municipality, local academic institutions, and suppliers. Two avenues have been explored, respectively partnering with small contractors able to meet the demand by working together or supporting entrepreneurs to meet the requirements of tenders. Current suppliers could first be approached to assess their current limits of meeting new needs. The Danish Design Centre could act as the organiser of the challenge and work on finding private or public investors to fund the challenge. The main levers of implementation on which the key sub actions rely on regard developing innovative partnerships and capacity building.

Score products

This last critical action reviewed addresses the creation of a scoring system for plastic healthcare products. In this action, the Municipality of Vejle and the regional procurement departments will pilot a scoring system for healthcare products. This scoring system will need to be based on LCAs to rank the products based on their environmental impact (e.g. CO₂-emissions). A rating system will need to be developed in

⁷¹<https://ddc.dk/>

⁷²<https://www.kl.dk/>

⁷³<https://www.essity.com/>

combination with a decision-making tool for procurement. Scoring products will require a methodological analysis performed most likely by a research institution and a technological platform to easily identify products. This tool should be developed in close partnership between local healthcare institutions, the municipality, and the Ministry of Environment department to align the government's priorities and the score.

Critical dependencies

Regarding the Sofiegården, the main critical dependency that derives from the identification of critical actions is the need for funding the innovation challenge. The funding can provide longevity of the project in the future. The target envisions a reduction of 25% less plastic to be sent to incineration in Sofiegården, specifically by diverting or replacing diapers.

Impact

The impacts (financial, social, and environmental) related to reducing plastic products in healthcare and diverting plastic waste in healthcare from incineration will be explained in detail in the deliverables D7.5, D1.5, and D3.3. In those, business models, the social return on investments, and the environmental impacts are respectively described. The scalability factor to evaluate the potential environmental impacts of the solution on a 5-year timescale is described by implementing the Mobile Sorting Station in the 17 other elderly centres in Vejle.

8. CONCLUSION

This report presents the process and outcomes of each REFLOW pilot city's urban ecosystem design as performed by WP 5 within the last year of the project. In the process, the purpose of the task has been twofold: to create a unified and replicable methodology that represents each pilot path in relation to their goal, by incorporating actions, stakeholders, and governance and its instruments as levers to complete the ecosystem. The overarching applied methodologies and the set of exercises –from the Circular Loops Diagram to the Backcasting– have supported and guided the creation of the final blueprints applied in each use case proposed by every pilot.

Starting from the identification of main actors per each pilot, the impacts of their actions to the material flow (i.e. Circular Loops), the simple and replicable strategy has coordinated the steps, levers, key sub-actions in pursuing the final goal elaborated in the Backcasting exercise. The consequent use cases analysed match the use cases selected in task 5.4 with the technical implementation of Reflow OS, with a few exceptions. The continuity in the process has allowed the pilots to start the implementation of these use cases during the time span of the REFLOW Project. As an outcome of the T5.3 exercise, the pilots have an overview of their pathway to change, what are the next steps, stakeholders, and what CE levers need to be operated. More generally, the task has contributed to creating collective know-how applicable and a methodology that can be applied and transferred to other pilots in the future, beyond REFLOW. This set of exercises has attempted to maintain the balance between the pilots' specificities, and the replicability and transferability of knowledge, procedures, and pitfalls stemming from these exercises.

Key takeaways and insights have emerged through these activities which help evidence the complexity of the REFLOW ambition and method, the differences and similarities between pilot cities, and how the various theoretical and technical building blocks of the REFLOW concept support the project's objectives going forward:

Benefits of the approach

The set of exercises developed through this task and described in this deliverable provided several benefits to the REFLOW pilot teams. Building an understanding of the different supply chains surrounding the material of focus for a city (i.e. Circular Loops), helped the pilot to uncover at which stages in the supply chains, a city and its different stakeholders involved in the pilot may or may not have influence on their material flow of focus. Additionally, this process created a strong foundation of knowledge on the current city's ecosystem and supported the pilot in keeping a systemic point of view (the 'big picture') while developing specific circular solutions in different components of the city's ecosystems. The solutions developed by the pilot could thus be visualised within their ecosystem - where various points of influence and stakeholders interact with each other, avoiding the 'silos' approach that can sometimes occur with urban initiatives.

Overall, the succession of the exercises led to the creation of blueprints bringing all aspects (governance, environmental, business, and social) of each city's solution together and yielded actionable insights - first by placing the solution within the city ecosystem, defining the key goal of the solution, and then elaborating a stepwise timeline to achieve it (i.e., Backcasting exercise).

More specifically, the Backcasting exercise nudged the pilot team to concretize their future visions for their circular solution, not only by co-identifying key barriers and challenges that will need to be overcome, but by

devising a succession of actions that will target each of these challenges. Thus, identifying current and future barriers helped the pilot team to connect future actions with their present actions. As each action requires specific stakeholder groups, the pilots were also compelled to identify the key stakeholders that will need to be brought onboard in the future, and plan their own involvement within the critical actions that must be taken to achieve the vision in the future.

Finally, beyond future actions that will need to take place, the Backcasting exercise provided the space to reflect on past actions and accomplishments to bring forward these solutions.

Replication of the process by cities

This deliverable should be read as a guidebook for other cities to replicate the process and implement circular solutions. The full suite of tools engaged within the scope of this exercise are available for review and use in the REFLOW Governance Toolkit (D4.3). For any city that would like to replicate the process shown in the above report, the suggested setup of the exercise is as follows:

- *Starting point:* Ideally, the cities should start with the knowledge of the material stream or sector of concern they would like to address. This can be achieved through mapping the material flows within the city to identify hotspots of the most impactful and abundant material flows. With this information, the city can map the ecosystem surrounding this specific flow in a Circular Loops Diagram to identify the wide range of possible intervention points and future business cases applicable to the city. From the elaboration of this diagram, the core team or consortium that wants to develop circular solutions should be involved. To capture the full opportunities to develop circularity, this team should be composed of people with different backgrounds, ranging from the cities' decision makers to technical and social experts.
- *Timeframe of the process:* If done at the beginning of the project, the full suite of T5.3 exercises could support the setting of an initial action plan, where a project-period timeline can be defined with critical milestones. These exercises can also be re-implemented mid-way through a project as an iterative process to see the evolution of the solutions as you gain more knowledge and partnerships within the city. If done at the end of a project, it can support the planning of future actions and to act as a cumulation of all past actions in an overview, which in turn can support self-reflection and course correction.
- *Configuration of partners:* To achieve the setting of a realistic goal for the future, it is vital to have a mix of key stakeholders participating in the initial exercises, including those in a decision-making position for the city. The presence of one or two long-term partners associated with the solutions are also vital to ensure continuity and ownership of the resulting timeline and critical actions. To ensure that the actions are grounded in reality as well as ensure meaningful contributions, it is essential to include knowledge partners and field experts of the relevant sector/material stream.

Next steps of REFLOW pilots

The REFLOW pilots have co-developed a 5-year timeline and future critical actions which identify their progress milestones for next 5 years, beyond REFLOW. Keeping this exercise as a blueprint for future iterations will support the identification of the growth of their initiatives and the evolution of the specific solutions. Future partnerships required for each critical action have been identified to a certain extent in the future, as well as any future funding required to help support the achievement of each pilot city's 5 year goal. The pilots are now aware of any and all immediate actions required to sow the seeds for future actions. Beyond the scope of the solutions discussed in

the above deliverable, many pilots have identified future potential circular loops through the circular loop diagram exercise, which can be explored further beyond REFLOW to support the overall circular transition of their city.

